

Measuring pedestrian and bicycle traffic

Methods and possibilities for Uppsala

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Executive summary

Introduction

The purpose of this report is to inform Uppsala Municipality on possibilities to strengthen its capacity to collect and use (digital) data on bicycle and pedestrian traffic.

It describes various methods to measure bicycle and pedestrian traffic and the current practice of measuring in Uppsala and provides recommendations to further develop a data-driven approach towards bicycle- and pedestrian planning.

It is based on literature studies as well as a survey, interviews and two workshops with staff from Uppsala Municipality.

Key results

Current situation:

- Uppsala is a successful cycling city and considerable knowledge about cycle traffic already exists within the organisation. Additional data can be valuable to support future planning, but its benefit has to be clear before engaging new measurements.
- Uppsala does have data on bicycle traffic from several measuring-points, but data-collection and management seems to be organised in an ad-hoc manner rather than strategically to answer specific questions or to provide information that directly can be used in planning.
- The existing, permanent counting stations can provide relevant baseline information but their number and location limit the strategic use of this data.
- The existing data is not yet readily accessible and put to use throughout the municipal organisation. Internal mechanisms and routines to systematically put bicycle-data to use in planning processes seem largely missing.
- Data on pedestrian traffic is scarce and only used to a little extend.

Measurement methods

- Many methods and sensor technologies can be used to gather information on bicycle- and pedestrian traffic.
- A single data-source or sensor-technology that can provide data on the movement of cyclists and pedestrians with high spatial and temporal resolution in real time, is cheap, provides full control over data, high levels of representativity and no privacy issues does not yet exist – and probably never will.
- No currently existing method can on its own provide all the necessary data planning. However, by combining results from different methods, additional insights can be gained.

- Methods that collect trajectory-data from cyclists or pedestrians – e.g. by GPS-tracking, can potentially provide rich data on traffic flows and route-preferences. However, these methods only provide data from a relatively small sample of cyclists or pedestrians and are not necessarily representative.
- Traditional “gate-counts”, measuring the number of passages at a certain location are still necessary to provide reliable information.
- Camera-based systems are developing rapidly and can provide additional information compared to more traditional measuring methods.

Data processing, storage and integration

- Bicycle- and pedestrian-traffic data needs to be systematically collected, processed and stored to be used to its full potential. This is more important than what data-acquisition method is used.
- Trajectory-based data is considerably more complex to process and use than traditional counter-data and might require new skills.
- Metadata is essential to be able to interpret measurement results and always need to be included.
- In the long run, a common repository for bicycle- and pedestrian data is necessary.
- Bicycle- and pedestrian data needs to be processed into information that can inform relevant decisions. This processing requires both data-skills as well as a good understanding of the needs of the receiver.
- A specialised function to organise and process data might become necessary in the future.

Key recommendations

- Before engaging in new measurements, define what information is desired, why and how it will be put to use.
- Uppsala should create a systematic overview on the existing data about walking and cycling.
- Identify knowledge-gaps and what information is lacking. First after this step, suitable methods to gather the necessary data should be considered.
- Complement the existing, permanent counting stations for bicycle traffic with additional counters to provide a solid set of base-data on cycle traffic that can be used on its own but also to calibrate other measurements.
- Consider camera-based systems for future measurement stations.
- Create a repository for bicycle- and pedestrian data where all relevant data is stored and accessible broadly within the municipality.
- Process measurement-data into information that is adapted to the needs and capability of the users.

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1 Introduction

1.1 BACKGROUND

This feasibility-study looks into the possibilities to collect data about pedestrian and bicycle movement and to make it accessible for the analysis, evaluation and planning of traffic infrastructure as well as the urban built environment and public spaces in general, crowd management in connection with major events and other possible uses, with a focus on digital data. The study is part of Uppsala Municipality's efforts to become a more digital and data-driven organisation within the traffic domain and to explore possibilities to collect and use digital data in a systematic way. Uppsala Municipality has the goal to become one of Europe's most digital cities by 2050.

Already today, Uppsala is one of Sweden's leading cycling cities and wants to further increase the use of sustainable modes of travel such as walking and cycling. Better knowledge and up-to-date data about the use of these modes can support this goal since it allows for better planning of infrastructure and facilitate evaluation of permanent or temporary measures.

Up-to-date data is also a prerequisite for understanding where maintenance should be prioritised as well as to detect where and when crowding occurs (e.g. at events) so that appropriate measures can be taken. Additionally, there is a growing interest in understanding how people use and interact with the urban built environment and public spaces which may be informed by such data. Accurate, detailed, and up-to-date data on walking and cycling can also facilitate the development of targeted marketing measures.

Currently, Uppsala has only a handful of measuring stations providing continuous data on cycle traffic and conducts additional temporary measurements of cycle traffic. Concerning pedestrian traffic, the available information is even more scarce. The city therefore wants to explore possibilities to collect and process more data on walking and cycling, using the possibilities of digital technologies. Further it wants to better understand how the collection, storage and processing of such digital data could be organised within the municipal organisation and how relevant data could be made available within as well as outside of the municipal organisation.

Vinnova, Sweden's innovation agency, funds this effort by the city of Uppsala within Vinnova's programme on the *Internet of Things*, aiming at creating societal value through increased digital connectivity.

1.2 PURPOSE AND GOALS

Purpose

The overarching purpose of this pre-study is to strengthen Uppsala Municipality's capacity to collect data on walking and cycling and to use this data for well-informed infrastructure- and city-planning, infrastructure management as well as evaluation of previous interventions.

With good knowledge of user behaviour, the infrastructure- and public space-offers can be better adapted to user needs, but also maintenance and safety-measures can be improved and better planned. This demands access to data about pedestrian- and bicycle movements and other traffic data with a high spatial and temporal resolution. Access to high-resolution data also allows for learning through more dynamic testing of measures since the impact can be followed more directly. This opens for new possibilities to test and evaluate measures and to better understand the impact of different interventions.

The increased use of digital technology as well as the possibility to store and process large quantities of digital data opens new options to collect and use data on the movement of pedestrians and cyclists. This also creates new challenges that need to be addressed such as

- Access to and ownership of data
- Privacy issues
- Keeping data alive and up-to date, i.e., building a community around data
- Developing methods, tools and algorithms as well as skills and capacity for extracting useful information
- Making data accessible to both experts and laymen
- Motivation of stakeholders to share their data

This study should support Uppsala Municipality in its efforts to become an attractive, human-centred city, to improve its capacity and efficiency in bicycle- and pedestrian planning and to use different data sources while addressing the challenges above. It aims at building in-house knowledge and capacity about collecting and using data about bicycle and pedestrian traffic.

It should further support the city's goal to become a data-driven organisation which uses the possibilities offered by digital data.

Project goals

The project goals are:

- To describe the current availability and use of bicycle- and pedestrian data in the municipality.
- To provide an overview over technical systems for collecting data on bicycle- and pedestrian traffic, with a description of their properties, advantages and disadvantages.
- To provide examples of other cities that systematically collect and process data on bicycle- and pedestrian traffic using digital tools.
- To provide recommendations on what solutions best could meet Uppsala's aspirations and could be scaled up.
- To clarify Uppsala's current readiness to process and use this kind of data.

- To provide recommendations on what organisational structures are suitable to enable efficient processing and use of empirical traffic data within the organisation.
- To provide recommendations for at stepwise development of capacity and increased collection and use of data on walking and cycling.

An additional goal is internal capacity building throughout the municipal organization by furthering internal discussions, knowledge and inter-departmental exchange on the collection, storage and use of data on pedestrian and bicyclist movement.

1.3 METHODS, PROJECT DESIGN

Description of technologies

Information concerning methods and technology for acquisition of data on cyclist- and pedestrian-movements has been collected through extensive web searches, literature reviews and interviews with representatives for cities and manufacturers.

Information about the efforts by other cities have been collected through literature reviews and interviews with representatives from cities and manufacturers.

Insight in the current state and needs of Uppsala Municipality

To better understand how the municipal organisation works with data about walking and cycling and data management today, both a **survey** and **interviews** were conducted, as well as meetings with the project's steering group in the city. Information was collected about what data already is available and from what sources, who is involved, who is a (potential) user of data and what outlook different municipal stakeholders have in this field.

For the survey, an online questionnaire was designed and sent to 26 internal stakeholders, selected by the project steering group within the municipality. The selected group consisted of municipal staff from different departments who were considered users or potential users of data on walking and cycling (e.g. from the traffic department, strategic planners), involved in data-acquisition, processing or organisation of digital data (e.g from the IT-department). 15 persons participated in the survey. See appendix 1 for survey questions and results.

To provide additional and more qualitative insight into the current situation and the needs of the organisation, a few respondents were selected for interviews. The main goal of conducting these interviews was to better understand the needs and goals of the city and its current capacity concerning analysis and use of data and technological readiness. The interviews were semi-structured with a prepared set of questions and the possibility for open questions and comments. Five interviews with selected stakeholders were conducted. See appendix 2 for a list of interviewees and interview results.

Workshops

Two workshops with staff from Uppsala municipality were conducted.

The workshop had multiple purposes:

- To introduce and discuss the topic of collecting and using pedestrian- and bicycle-data to the participants and thus build better understanding and knowledge.
- To extract more information on the needs of the city and on its technical readiness and capacity.
- To use the collective knowledge and experience of all participants to give input to the process of improved data-acquisition and data-use.

Workshop 1, held on the 25th of August 2021 had the title *What do we know and what do we want to measure? (Vad vill vi veta, vad ska vi mäta?)*. 26 persons from the city administration participated, all directly or indirectly involved in traffic planning, data-management, or strategic planning. The workshop focused on introducing the topic of pedestrian- and bicycle-data, on generating better understanding of the possibilities and challenges with more data and on identifying the participants needs and wishes concerning data.

Workshop 2, held on the 13th of October 2021 focused on the process of how to achieve the desired results and what steps that need to be taken. Eight persons from Uppsala Municipality participated, as well as external experts from the cities of Copenhagen, Amsterdam, Berlin and Zürich. The workshop was inspired by the six steps of the *Design Sprint*¹ methodology.

1.4 TEAM

This project has been conducted during 2021 and early 2022 on behalf of Uppsala Municipality by **Koucky & Partners AB**, Gothenburg, supported by **Metascapes** (Copenhagen) and the Department of Geoinformatics of the **University of Salzburg**.

Following persons contributed:

- Bernhard Snizek (Metascapes)
- Michael Koucky (Koucky & Partners)
- Alex Spielhaupter (Koucky & Partners)
- Martin Loidl (Department of Geoinformatics, University of Salzburg)

Main contact person at Uppsala municipality was Ola Kahlström, supported by Sara Andersson and Karl Nygren.

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Design_sprint

2 Measuring walking and cycling – why and what?

2.1 WHY MEASURING?

Data is not information

There are many reasons for cities to collect data on walking and cycling and on traffic in general. Fundamentally, collecting data should enable to answer questions that are relevant for decision making that leads to action.

Picture 2.1: The process from data to actions. Data in itself is not information, it needs to be processed, interpreted and put in context before it can serve decision-making

A clear distinction needs to be made between data and processed information. Processed information is here used to describe the knowledge needed for well-informed decision making. Data is what can be collected through different measurements and is hardly ever directly usable for decision making but needs to be processed and interpreted so that the desired questions can be answered with satisfactory reliability.

Usually, processed information comprises of one or several **indicators** that aggregate and simplify available data in such a form that it becomes useable for decision making and comparison over time. That could for example be the modal share of cycling or walking in the city, total kilometres cycled, the level of satisfaction of cyclists in the municipality, the number of passages across an inner-city ring, the number of reported bicycle-accidents in relation to cycling volumes, pedestrians' perception of security etc.

What kind of questions that should be answered and what decisions will be based on this information are fundamental concerns that need to be raised **before** engaging in data-collection. Ideally, also the question of how precise and reliable the information needs to be so that it is suitable for decision making is answered at an early stage.

For many questions, different ways to find answers are available. An example is the question of whether a certain section of infrastructure needs improvements, e.g. if a pedestrian- or bicycle-lane is wide enough for its level of use. This could be determined by measuring peak-flows and using design-manual reference values to determine whether it is wide enough for the measured flow. Another option to obtain similar information could be to measure the level of satisfaction of the users of the section in question to determine whether they find it to narrow or not.

In some cases, data from different sources needs to be combined to find an answer.

What question that should be **answered** and how **robust** the information needs to be should always come first. Once this is clearly defined, different ways to answer it and what data is necessary to do so can be explored, as well as different methods to collect the necessary data. **Data on its own has little to no value, and even processed information is of little value if it is not used to inform the decision-making process.**

Motives for gathering information

There are several motives to provide decision-makers with information on walking and cycling.

Information on the levels of walking and cycling and their development over time is instrumental to be able to judge whether political goals for these modes are met or whether increased efforts are needed. It is further needed to create better facilities and to locate them where demand and need is the highest.

Further questions that can be relevant to answer are e.g.:

- Is the existing infrastructure adequate to meet the current and anticipated needs of cyclists and pedestrians? If not, where are improvements needed? Where are investments most efficiently used?
- What was the impact of previous interventions, e.g. infrastructure investments? Can the organisation learn from this information for future interventions and improve its future design and planning?
- Where should maintenance be prioritised to achieve best results?
- What levels of maintenance are adequate?
- Is there a need to improve traffic safety and if so, where?
- How satisfied are local cyclists and pedestrians? Can their level of satisfaction be increased and how?
- Where should cycle parking be placed and how many places are needed?
- What urban form and design features are encouraging the use of walking and cycling and how can this be integrated in future planning?
- What locations are suitable for development if a large share of walking and cycling is desired?
- Is there a difference in travel behaviour between different groups and why?
- Can travel times for cyclists and pedestrian be improved, e.g. by junction design and signal management?
- What are the quantified/monetized benefits of walking and cycling?
- Where and when does risk for undesirable crowding occur?

2.2 WHAT CAN BE MEASURED AND HOW

There are several types or categories of pedestrian- and bicycle-data. In this section, the following common categories of data are shortly described.

- Travel behaviour – population level
- User experience
- Bicycle parking use
- Accident data
- Gate-counts
- Areal-counts
- Trajectories

Travel behaviour – population level

Travel behaviour data on a population level describes primarily how many trips people do on average and what distances they travel. Often, travel behaviour data also consists of information on to what extent different traffic modes are chosen, origin and destination of trips, the purpose of trips and demographic background information. Typically, information on travel behaviour on a population level is gathered through travel surveys based on a statistical sample, but also cell tower mobile phone positioning data can to some extent provide information on travel behaviour on a population level.

Travel behaviour data is typically used to follow large-scale trends in traffic behaviour such as the development of travel distances and of the modal split. If information on origin and destination of trips is available, it can also support infrastructure planning.

User experience

Data on user experience can for example contain data on the level of satisfaction of cyclists, the sense of security of pedestrians in a certain area, which areas are perceived as unsafe or where infrastructure is deemed insufficient etc. It collects information on the subjective experience of users rather than from physical measurements and can provide insight in what factors influences user behaviour. If combined with demographic information, it can also allow for analysis of the needs or opinions of specific groups. User experience data can be connected to a precise geographic location (e.g. a certain road, crossing, area) or be more general, e.g. the general level of satisfaction with cycling infrastructure. Examples are the reported satisfaction levels in the *Copenhagen Bicycle Account* or the results of the user-study “*Cyklstvelometer*” that is regularly conducted in several Swedish cities, including Uppsala². User experience data, especially when it also contains geographical information, can be used to identify areas where improvements are possible without using physical measurements. To some extent, the users can be used as “living sensors”. User experience data is typically collected by interviews or surveys, but also digital tools can be used. Examples of digital tools are apps or webpages designed for reporting faults in the infrastructure or digital survey tools, some with map-functions to localise problem areas. Another example is the project *PING if you care!* that was conducted in Brussels in 2017. 1 000 voluntary cyclists were equipped with a

² City of Copenhagen, 2019: *Bicycle Account 2018* and Uppsala kommun, 2021: *Cykelbokslut 2020*

special button on the handlebar of their bikes that they could easily push every time they felt distressed or unsatisfied when cycling in the city³. The button was connected by Bluetooth to the user's phone and a specific app would record and transmit the location of each event. In that way, the city could in a short period of time create a map indicating locations with high levels of cyclist dissatisfaction

Also "low-tech" approaches such as a systematic follow-up of complaints reported by users can be seen as a way to gather data based on user experience.

Parked bicycles

The number of parked bikes in a specific area can be counted and can provide information on important destinations for cyclists as well as information on where additional bicycle parking facilities are needed. With repeated counts at different times, the number of parked bikes can also provide information on the daily movement of bicycles in and out of a defined area.

Accident data

Data on the number and location of traffic accidents involving pedestrians and cyclists can be used to identify locations or situations with increased risk as well as provide metrics on the level of safety for pedestrians and cyclists. For more severe accidents, data can be collected from police and hospital records or from the Swedish national traffic accident database STRADA. For less severe accidents that do not require police or ambulance intervention, accident data can only be collected through self-reporting by accident victims or witnesses.

Some camera-based measurement system can detect collisions. This information is however only indicative for the safety level on the specific location that is covered, not for an entire network.

Gate counts

Gate counts register the number of cyclists or pedestrians that cross an imaginary "gate" or a line across a street or path during a specific time. Gate counting is the most common approach to measure vehicular traffic, both for motorized traffic and for bicycles.

Picture 2.2: Gate-counts register passages through a measuring line or -field. Some gate-counts simply accumulate the number of passed objects, others register each passage with a time-stamp for further processing.

³ See: <https://pingifyoucare.eu/> and <https://civitas.eu/tool-inventory/ping-if-you-care>

Gate-count data can be gathered in many different ways, from manual counts to pneumatic tubes reacting on pressure, radar, inductive loops that react to metal objects passing, infrared-sensor and camera-based systems.

Independent of the chosen measurement method, the output is the number of passages in a certain period. Certain system can further differentiate between the direction of travel of the passing objects, the mode of transport and measure travel speed. Simple gate-counters add up the number of passages in a given timeframe, while more sophisticated models register each passage with a timestamp.

Gate counts can provide information on the development of the number of passages at a specific location over time. Depending on the way passages are recorded and over how long time, they can also provide information on the distribution of passages over a day or a year.

If two gate-counts along the same route are performed at different locations and no deviations from the route are possible within this section, this can provide information on the number of pedestrians or cyclists within the sector at a given time.

Areal counts

Areal counts describe the number or the change of the number of counting objects (e.g. cyclists, pedestrians, cars) within a defined area in a specific time. It is typically based on aggregation of data from gate-counts on all in- and outgoing routes to the area. For smaller areas, area counts can also be conducted by Wi-Fi/Bluetooth or camera-based equipment that can measure the number of counting objects more directly.

If counting-equipment with high temporal resolution and continuous counting is used on all counting stations, areal counts can provide detailed information on the increase or decrease of counting objects within the area at all times, e.g. the change of the number of people within a pedestrian zone or a specific street, the change of the number of cars in the inner city etc.

Picture 2.3: Areal counts describe the total number of counting objects in an area or the number entering and leaving the area in a given time-interval. They are typically conducted by aggregating results from gate-counts at all entry/exit points to the area or by direct counts or measurements of the number of objects present.

Area counts are common in car-traffic measurement and often described as rings, e.g. inner- or outer-city ring, counting all in- and outgoing vehicles in a defined urban area. Uppsala also uses an inner-city ring (Innerstadssnitt) for measuring car-traffic to and from the centre.

An example where the concept also is used for bicycle traffic is the inner-city ring (*Innerstadssnitt*) in Stockholm, where bikes entering or leaving the area are counted on 14 gate-points – see picture 2.4.

Picture 2.4: Areas in Stockholm where areal-counts are conducted. Entering and exiting bicycle traffic is measured for the dark blue area, Innerstadssnittet. Source: SL

If areal counts are performed for several neighbouring areas in a grid, areal counts can also provide information on the movements between different areas and information on origins and destinations of trips (OD-matrices).

Trajectories

Trajectories describe the movement of a specific vehicle or person over time by datasets that consist of position and time data. By connecting the separate measuring points the trajectory can be approximated, as illustrated by picture 2.5.

Picture 2.5: By connecting locations recorded at different times, a trajectory of a moving object can be constructed. The higher the precision of spatial information and the higher the sampling frequency, the more precise the trajectory becomes.

The higher the sampling frequency and the more precise the location can be determined at each sampling point, the more accurate the trajectory becomes. Common ways to collect trajectory-data is GPS-tracking with dedicated trackers or via the built in GPS-function in mobile phones. Trajectories can also be

extracted from cell-tower mobile phone positioning, networks of Wi-Fi/Bluetooth sensors or, for small areas, through camera-based measurements. Trajectories can be collected with or without the active knowledge and consent of the person being tracked, the later causing concerns about privacy issues.

Picture 2.6 – multiple, unprocessed trajectories of cyclists in the city of Ljubljana, collected with dedicated GPS-trackers for the research project CyCity. Source: Tominc et al. 2012

Trajectories also allow for calculating the speed between two measuring points since the distance can be approximated and the time difference is known. The higher the sampling frequency and the more accurate the location is measured, the more precise the speed estimate becomes. For high-frequency data such as GPS-tracks, speed and time of stand-still can be determined with relatively high accuracy for each location along the track.

For most planning uses, trajectories of individual trips or even all trips by one person are of little interest. However, if a large number of individual trajectories is aggregated, relevant information can be extracted. If, for example, the trajectories are allocated to their nearest sections of the (road) network, the number of trajectories for each section can indicate how intensely the sections are used relatively to each other. This is often illustrated with so called heat-maps, indicating the (relative) intensity of use, see picture 2.7. This information can be useful to identify highly used routes so that improvement or maintenance of cycle infrastructure can be prioritised systematically.

Picture 2.7: Heat map that illustrates the number of recorded tracks on road segments in Vienna, indicating the intensity of cycling. Red segments are most intensely used. Picture: BikeCitizen

In theory, aggregated trajectories can provide very rich data relevant for traffic planning. For example, cycling volumes could theoretically be estimated at any specific point of the network and for any time given sufficiently detailed heat-maps. Further, speed-distribution and where waiting times occurs can be illustrated based on aggregated trajectories – an example is illustrated in picture 2.8.

Where and how long do people have to wait at crossings? Example shows Vienna. Graphic: Bike Citizens

Picture 2.8: Distribution of waiting time at junctions for cyclists in Vienna. Red areas indicate places with average waiting times over 45 seconds. Picture: Bike Citizen.

However, the reliability and useability of trajectory-based data is highly dependent on:

- the number of aggregated trajectories
- how large the proportion of tracked trips is to actual trips
- the representativeness of the sample-group,
- the level of accuracy of the position-data and sampling frequency and
- knowledge of what modes of traffic has been used.

Especially a thorough understanding of the accuracy and margin of error of the position data is important.

Trajectory-data does not in itself contain information on what type of traffic mode is used. This can in some cases be determined by selecting a data-collection method that excludes all unwanted modes (e.g. by specifically targeting cyclists and ask them to actively contribute with trajectory data) or by analysis of trajectory data where the mode for each trajectory is estimated by parameters such as speed or mode-specific location (e.g. a highway, railway-track). In locations where several modes can have similar speed (e.g. low-speed zones in cities) or if the geographical position cannot be determined with suitable precision, the distinction of modes is however difficult in a post-analysis.

2.3 TEMPORARY VS CONTINUOUS DATA COLLECTION

Traffic data can be collected continuously or during a limited timeframe. This influences what information can be extracted, what questions can be answered and with what accuracy conclusions can be drawn from the collected data.

Historically, information on walking and cycling flows has to a large extent been collected through temporary measurements, e.g., through manual counts or automated gate counts during timeframes from one day up to several weeks. However, levels of walking and cycling are not only influenced by long term trends but can also fluctuate on a daily basis due to e.g., weather conditions and between seasons due to changes in temperature and precipitation. Also changes in the surrounding of the measuring position, e.g., temporary road works can influence the result. When comparing and interpreting data on walking and cycling flows from temporary counts, it is therefore instrumental to understand for how long and when data has been collected and to have additional information such as temperature and weather conditions during that period as well as awareness of any important temporary changes in the surroundings that might have had an influence on the results.

Continuous data collection with automated methods provides a more robust basis for interpretation. It provides a larger data set where short-term fluctuations easier can be identified and dealt with. The daily-, weekly- or seasonal variation become clearer and the importance of seasons or weather conditions, but also other temporary disturbances, can be analysed.

Continuous data collection provides more valuable information concerning traffic flows than temporary measurements. However, temporary measurements of traffic flows can still be relevant for specific questions or if the data is interpreted carefully and with consideration of influencing factors.

Picture 2.9 illustrates annual fluctuations on an example from Stockholm. The city counts passing bicycles on a series of measuring points where annual temporary measurements are conducted, covering passages in and out of the inner city (inner-city ring, *Innerstadssnittet* – see picture 2.4). The results fluctuate significantly between the years. For example, the number of passages fell significantly from 2016 to 2017 (75 900 passages 2016, 56 700 passages 2017, a reduction by 25%) but rose again drastically to 86 000 – 50% more than in the previous - year just to fall back to 76 800 passages in 2019.

The results need to be interpreted with consideration of the weather conditions during each measurement period – 2017 was considerably colder and rainier

than both 2016 and 2018. A direct comparison of annual data could easily lead to misleading conclusions about the long-term development of cycling in Stockholm. To compensate for the significant fluctuation of annual counts, Stockholm uses rolling five-year averages to be able to detect the long-term developments of cycling.

Picture 2.9: Annual number of cyclists passing the inner-city measuring ring (Innerstadssnittet) in Stockholm. The orange line represents actual annual counts, the blue line a rolling five-year average. Source: Miljöbarometern, Stockholm Stad.

3 Challenges when collecting and using traffic data

3.1 RELIABILITY OF RESULTS

Measuring always demands a trade-off between the precision and reliability of results and costs. This must be kept in mind when planning the collection of data and during interpretation of data. Good knowledge about the properties and understanding of the limitations of the chosen method is essential.

How reliable and exact the data needs to be to answer the asked questions appropriately and to inform decision-making is ideally determined prior to any measurement campaign. If existing data is used, it is essential to not only include measurement-results but also information on its reliability and margin of error and to take these into account.

This can be exemplified by how the sample-size in traditional travel surveys where both the statistical reliability of results as well as the cost to collect data increases with a higher number of samples. An acceptable trade-off between cost and reliability must therefore be determined. Care must be taken not to draw conclusions based on data from surveys with insufficient sample-size.

Data-collecting sensors can have technical limitations that need to be considered. Most sensors that count passages of pedestrians or cyclists (gate counts) typically produce reliable counts if passages occur one-by-one. However, in situations with high flows, where cyclists or pedestrians can pass the measuring line besides each other, not all passages might be recorded. This leads to an underestimation of the number of passages during high-flow situations. Even video-based systems can have limitation, e.g. when the light conditions are poor or when the camera units line of vision is blocked.

When methods that produce location data are used, their spatial precision needs to be understood. Temporary measuring campaigns might be influenced by the weather conditions during the measuring period or other temporary factors which need to be taken into account (see chapter 2.3.).

To be able to properly interpret measurement data, it is essential to always have access to metadata with information about the way the data has been collected, by what method and knowledge of relevant surrounding circumstances.

3.2 SPATIAL AND TEMPORAL RESOLUTION

Spatial resolution

When collecting and interpreting data that includes spatial information on the location of the measured object – usually trajectories – the spatial and temporal resolution as well as its margin of error need to be considered. The spatial resolution must be suitable for the question at hand. To understand regional transport patterns for example, a spatial precision on the scale of kilometres is

sufficient. However, for the analysis of walking- and cycling-movements within a specific urban area, a precision of a few meters or even higher might be necessary.

The technology used determines what precision is possible, but also local circumstances like building height or the density of mobile phone base stations can influence the precision of the results.

For example, GPS-enabled smartphones are typically accurate to within a radius of about 5 meters under open sky. However, the accuracy decreases near buildings, bridges and trees due to satellite signal blockage or signal reflection⁴.

The accuracy of WiFi- or Bluetooth-beacon based systems is determined by the density of the network of used antennas and can vary from a few metres to dozens of metres.

Location data based on cell tower mobile phone positioning is far less accurate since the location is determined by the location of the cell tower that a specific phone has been connected to at a given time. The accuracy is thus dependent on the density of mobile phone cell towers and is typically in the range of 200 metres to one kilometre. In areas with a high density of cell phone towers, typically in urban areas, accuracy can be higher.

Camera-based systems on the other hand can provide very high accuracy in the range of centimetres, but only within the field of vision of the camera.

Temporal resolution

The temporal resolution in which data is collected and in which it is aggregated and stored determines what questions the measuring results can be used for. While a physical passage of a pedestrian or a cyclist occurs at a specific time, the time of each passage is not recorded in all measurement systems. Gate and area-counts as well as trajectory data are typically aggregated into counts per minutes, hours, days, weeks, months or even years.

The level of aggregation depends on the measuring technology as well as the processing of the measured data. Data with high temporal resolution (e.g. when each count-event also has time-data associated to it) can always be aggregated to a lower resolution (hours to days etc.) but not vice versa.

Examples of data with high temporal resolution are individual GPS-tracks or gate-counts with precise timestamps. Examples of data with low temporal resolution are manual counts or aggregated data from GPS-routes that were collected over a long period.

The lowest level of temporal resolution of the available data determines what questions can be answered by it. Travel-speed estimation or the estimation of waiting times at crossings based on trajectory data demands a very high temporal resolution of the available data (seconds or better). To be able to estimate peak-flow levels and when they occur across a busy route, count-data should be available on an aggregation level of no more than 15 minutes. For other

⁴ <https://www.gps.gov/systems/gps/performance/accuracy/>

purposes, data that is aggregated on an hourly, daily, monthly or even annual level might be sufficient.

3.3 REPRESENTATIVENESS

When interpreting data, it is necessary to understand whether the selected sample represents the population as a whole or is biased towards a specific group, and whether that can influence the result. In surveys, this is typically controlled by collecting demographic data from the respondents such as age, sex, income levels or similar or by specifically recruiting the desired groups.

Physical measurements of pedestrian- or cyclist movements – e.g. line-measurement of passages - are normally not biased towards certain groups since the desired information is measured directly. Whoever passes the measuring line is counted. However, physical measurements cannot detect whether a specific group is over- or underrepresented amongst the people passing the measuring point and is thus not suitable for detecting differences in travel behaviour between demographic groups.

Cell tower mobile phone positioning data can be considered being representative for a large part of the population in countries with very high mobile phone usage such as Sweden. However, this method excludes smaller children without phones. This is also true for WiFi- or Bluetooth based position data, with the limitation that only phones with activated WiFi or Bluetooth are registered. Cell-phone based data without additional demographic information is not suitable for detecting differences in travel patterns between demographic groups, for the same reason as physical measurements. However, since cell tower positioning data also can contain information on the home location (night-location/no movement), it could theoretically be used to examine differences in travel patterns based on home-location areas.

Data from app-based services is not necessarily representative for the wider population. App-based positioning data requires that phone owners actively install and use one or several specific applications. This limits the number of users and the sample size. Depending on the application (or multiple applications) that is used to collect data, there might be a bias towards a specific age- or user-group and the data needs to be interpreted accordingly. An example is route-data collected through fitness-applications. This data can be biased in two ways: Firstly, fitness-apps are generally only used by people who exercise and want to document their training. Secondly, they are primarily used to track training sessions and even people using them might not necessarily track their everyday bicycle rides or walks.

When using and interpreting app-based data it is therefore necessary to have a good understanding on how this data has been collected, the sample size/number of people that have provided data as well as any possible bias.

3.4 PRIVACY

The issue of privacy becomes significant when data on passages or trajectories can be associated to a specific person, providing information about the whereabouts of that individual. This does not necessitate that the identity of that person is explicitly included in the data - it is enough that the identity could be

deduced by using the measurement data by combining it with other available information.

If this is the case, care has to be taken to avoid conflict with legislation on privacy and consent of the concerned individuals might be necessary. This is especially sensitive if measurement data is made public.

Examples of measurement data that could cause concern about privacy are:

- Data where information on location and time is associated to a specific device, e.g. a mobile phone, and device-identification data (e.g. the MAC-address or phone number) is stored. This can be the case with cell-tower mobile phone positioning data, data collected through WiFi/Bluetooth-systems and data collected through mobile phone apps.
- Data that is collected through cameras where the video-image is either processed directly with image-recognition software (e.g. numberplate recognition, face recognition) or where video data is stored and could be subject for later analysis that could lead to the identification of individuals.
- Travel patterns between specific locations that are associated with certain groups – e.g. places of worship (churches, synagogues, mosques), specific workplaces (police, military, social workers) or places associated to a specific political affiliation.

There are several possibilities to associate seemingly anonymous trajectories to an individual, e.g. by combining an analysis of trajectory data with information on residential- or work addresses or by observation. For vehicular traffic, information from numberplate recognition can be combined with trajectories. For persons, the same is technically possible with video-monitoring and face-recognition.

Privacy issues do not automatically exclude the collection of position-data from recognisable devices. The possibility to extract data on individuals can be reduced by separating device-id data from position- and temporal data or by ensuring that no video-images are stored.

The aggregation of data from many users or high temporal and/or spatial aggregation of data can also reduce privacy concerns. This can for example be done by aggregating all trip data from many users for one year or by allocating all location points to larger areas, removing information on the exact location by reducing the spatial resolution. However, each aggregation is associated with a loss of information and therefore it changes what questions that can be answered using the data. If, for example, raw data contains background-information on users (e.g. age, sex) that would allow an analysis based on these factors, this possibility is lost when these parameters are eliminated in an aggregated level. A high level of aggregation of position data makes the analysis of geographical movement patterns and origin-destination matrices less detailed.

In some cases, even aggregated data can be sensitive if not carefully managed, as illustrated in cases where the location of clandestine military bases was revealed by aggregated trajectories from fitness-apps used by staff⁵.

If data-collection technologies are used that could lead to the association of information to a specific individual or group, significant care must be taken concerning how this data is stored, processed and to whom it is made available. There is always a trade-off between privacy and the precision and richness of information when dealing with data that is collected in a way that could be associated to an individual.

3.5 DEPENDENCY ON A SUPPLIER

A municipality has full control and ownership of data it collects itself through physical measurements. Further, there are generally multiple possible providers of the necessary measurement equipment giving the municipality the possibility to choose and also to change provider.

However, if data is collected by a third-party provider that collects and processes the data, the level of control diminishes. This is the case with cell tower positioning data as well as for many of the app-based data providers. Some data providers even themselves purchase data, further reducing the level of control.

In these cases, control over how the data is collected and processed is limited and these services are only offered by few providers. What analysis is possible is often limited to the tools offered by the provider.

This reduces the municipality's control and possibility to freely choose or change provider. It also poses a risk of losing the continuity of data-series, e.g. if the provider goes out of business or chooses to terminate the service.

This should be considered when the collected data should be used for decision making or for following long-term traffic developments.

3.6 COST AND VALUE

Introduction

The cost of collecting data and processing it into useful information is a key factor when deciding what data should be collected, with what method, reliability and spatial and temporal resolution. Ultimately, collecting information always is a trade-off between precision and reliability of data and cost.

Prior to deciding on any investment in collecting data about walking- and cycling traffic (or any data for that matter), it should be considered what benefits and **value** the envisaged additional information can bring to the organisation. Value can e.g. include more efficient use or more equal distribution of maintenance or investment resources, shortened decision processes, improved service-levels to citizens, information for better long-term evaluation and planning, the

⁵ <https://www.wired.com/story/strava-heat-map-military-bases-fitness-trackers-privacy/>

possibility to conduct more targeted and efficient information campaigns or more.

It is inherently difficult to express these values in monetary terms, but efforts should be made to state the positive impact the expected information can have to be able to compare it with the costs of collecting and processing data. Expressed differently, it is necessary to judge what additional information is worth to the organisation.

This can help to set a financial framework for data-collection that can facilitate the choice of both method and adequate precision and resolution.

Once benefits of additional information have been identified, the next step is to reflect on what data can provide this information and what minimum quality of data (resolution, density of sensor-network, representativity, precision etc) is necessary to achieve the desired outcome.

Cost elements

Cost of data collection and processing consists of several key elements:

- Planning– choice of location, design of measuring system, procurement costs
- Investment– cost of the measurement equipment/service
- Installation / setup
- Training of staff for maintenance and for use of data
- Recruitment and marketing – for user-based systems (apps, surveys)
- Operation– energy, maintenance, data-transfer cost, staff cost
- Licensing and support
- Data storage
- Data processing
- Dissemination of results

For data-collecting methods that rely on users sharing information like dedicated apps, surveys or interviews, the cost of recruiting and maintaining the desired numbers of participants need to be estimated

Data processing implies the cost of extracting useful information from the data produced. This service can be performed in-house or outsourced, depending on the available capacity in-house and the complexity of data-processing. Labour cost for data processing can be difficult to judge but should always be considered. The more complex and rich the collected data, the higher cost for data processing can be expected since more qualified staff is needed.

Cost can also vary significantly, both between different data-acquisition methods as well as within the same method. It is therefore not possible to provide more than rough cost indications for different methods and cost-estimations need to be made on a case-to-case basis. When evaluating different data-collection systems, the total cost to acquire the desired data during the planned operational time needs to be considered, considering all elements presented above.

4 Examples from other cities

4.1 COPENHAGEN

Copenhagen is widely known as one of the world's leading cycling cities. 32% of all trips by the city's inhabitants are done by bike and 44% of all trips to and from work (2019)⁶.

Copenhagen has for many years focused on improving conditions for cycling and has built up a comprehensive set of bicycle-related data. Since 1970, Copenhagen has measured bicycle- and car-traffic systematically, counting both car- and cycle-traffic passing two "measuring-rings" – an outer ring on the municipal border and an inner-city ring (Søsnittet) – see picture 4.1.

Picture 4.1 & 4.2.: Locations of traffic-counting stations in Copenhagen. Source: Københavns Kommune, 2015: *Trafikken i København, Trafiktal 2010-2014*

Besides the measuring-gates forming the outer- and inner-city ring, additional measuring locations are spread across Copenhagen and Fredriksberg to provide complementary information on cycle traffic on the borough-level and on selected corridors.

Historically, traffic counts were performed manually during several counting sessions across the year to achieve average figures, using fixed locations. Gradually, automatic counters were installed on key locations for more permanent data collection. Currently (2021), the city operates 43 permanent bicycle counters, whereof 20 use video-based measuring systems and 23 use inductive loops. However, also temporary counts using pneumatic tubes and even manual counts

⁶ Københavns Kommune. (2020). *Cykelredegørelse 2020*.

are still used frequently for additional information. Counts of pedestrian traffic are also conducted, manually, but at significantly fewer locations.

The collected data is stored centrally and fed into the traffic management plattform *MobMaestro*⁷ where also information on car-traffic is stored and processed. The data is further accessible internally through the city-internal GIS-system and is used as input-data for traffic models. Count-data used to be publicly accessible through the public GIS-service of the City of Copenhagen (København kortet) that contains information on bicycle infrastructure⁸. However, this functionality has been removed from the public interface of the map for unknown reasons.

Picture 4.3 & 4.4.: Bicycle-count data in the Copenhagens GIS-system. Source: city of Copenhagen.

Copenhagen also regularly conducts surveys on user-satisfaction amongst cyclists – both on a general level as part of the city’s bicycle-account but also concerning specific locations as an additional tool to gather information relevant for traffic planning – see picture 4.5.

Picture 4.5: Results from a user-survey in bicycle-infrastructure in Copenhagen. Red dots indicate areas where cyclists reported that they lack a bike-lane, black dots indicate areas where the bike-lane is considered too narrow and blue dots crossings that are considered crowded. Source: City of Copenhagen

⁷ <https://www.technolution.com/move/mobimaestro/>

⁸ <https://kbhkort.kk.dk/spatialmap>

The methods used to collect data on cycling in Copenhagen are predominantly traditional, even manual counts are still used. However, the city collects and uses the data systematically and strategically. Copenhagen has developed internal capacity and knowledge to collect, store and process traffic- and other digital data and to make it available to traffic planners and strategists by establishing an internal "data unit". This unit is specialised in processing (digital) data and supports other units within the city with information they request.⁹

4.2 AMSTERDAM

Cycling-data

Amsterdam is another world-renowned bicycle city with very high levels of bicycle use. Amsterdam has, similarly to Copenhagen, an extensive counting programme using permanent sensors as well as temporary counts. Besides performing line-counts with pneumatic tubes, inductive loops, radar and cameras, the city also monitors parked bicycles and collects trajectory-data through the national initiative *Fietselweek* (bicycle counting week) where inhabitants are encouraged to track their bike-journeys using a specific mobile-app (see chapter 6 for technical information).

A key challenge for cycling in Amsterdam is space and data is used to facilitate cycling in parts of the city where space is scarce. Traffic data is used to ensure sufficiently wide cycle paths and logical routes to safely handle large numbers of cyclists, to identify and solve bottlenecks and missing links.¹⁰

Amsterdam also annually collects data on the satisfaction-level of cyclists. The so called *Cycling Satisfaction Monitor Amsterdam* was launched 2018 and data is collected through surveys amongst cyclists¹¹.

Processing and use of data

The city of Amsterdam has developed internal capacity and know-how to use and process data on bicycle and pedestrian traffic. It has employed specialist researchers on mobility and public space that collect and analyse bicycle-data and provide input to the city organisation.

Since 1990, Amsterdam has further established a platform and routine for sharing knowledge about research in the city internally and with external partners such as the Police, called the municipality-wide Research Consultation. The Research Consultation takes place every one and a half month and has a rotating chair/secretary every two meeting and constantly changing location. Each consultation consists of two substantive presentations of research, given by participants or invited guests. There is also room for knowledge sharing, open questions and coordination about research data and research programming. This established process is used to distribute knowledge across municipal departments but also to provide insight and ideas about the use of data, what

⁹ Jos van Vlerken, Municipality of Copenhagen, personal communication 2021; cz9y@kk.dk

¹⁰ Marten van der Lof, Mobility and Public Space researcher, City of Amsterdam, personal communication 2021.

¹¹ <https://bikecity.amsterdam.nl/en/inspiration/cycling-satisfaction-monitor-amsterdam/>

information is requested or already available. The units responsible for bicycle data and research on the use of public space are actively involved in these regular consultations¹².

Pedestrian monitoring

Amsterdam works actively with monitoring pedestrian flows and gatherings, primarily to avoid crowding in very busy areas. The city has established a *Crowd Monitoring System* with counting cameras and WiFi-sensors at sensitive spots that give real-time insight into to numbers and densities of pedestrians. If a situation risks to become unsafe because of crowding, measures can be taken to diffuse the situation, e.g. by using digital information boards to advise about alternative routes, by imposing one-way traffic to establish constant and safe pedestrian flow or by closing off roads. The city has also initiated a pilot project within the framework of the Crowd Monitoring System called *Public Eye* to continuously monitor the level of crowding in additional public spaces using already existing cameras¹³. In this project, real-time video data from third party cameras is sent to a server of the municipality where picture-analysis algorithms count the number of people. This information is then forwarded to municipal employees and facility managers to regulate traffic. The picture-data is neither saved nor shown. The information is also accessible to the public through the municipal webpage *Drukbeeld Amsterdam* (literally: pressure picture Amsterdam) that also shows congestion levels on streets and the occupancy of parking spots real time¹⁴.

Picture 4.6 & 4.7: Locations of Amsterdams Crowd Monitoring System that measures the number of pedestrians at certain key locations, using camera- or WiFi-based sensors. The information is available to the public through the municipal webpage "Drukbeeld Amsterdam" (Busy city Amsterdam). The webpage also contains information on traffic congestion and parking occupancy. Source: <https://drukbeeld.amsterdam.nl/>

¹² <https://openresearch.amsterdam.nl/page/33983/onderzoekersoverleg-amsterdam> and Marten van der Lof, personal communication.

¹³ <https://www.amsterdam.nl/innovatie/mobiliteit/public-eye/>

¹⁴ <https://drukbeeld.amsterdam.nl/>

The Crowd Monitoring System has been developed by the Innovation team of the City of Amsterdam together with the Mobility and Public Space department. It was first used during the large public event SAIL 2015 and is now permanently used in De Wallen, the medieval inner-city centre, at the Central Station bus platform and near the ferries.

5 Uppsala – current situation and outlook

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter describes our understanding of the current situation concerning the collection and use of data about pedestrian- or bicycle-traffic in Uppsala. It is primarily based on information gathered from city-staff through a survey, interviews and two workshops and the Uppsala bicycle account for 2020¹⁵.

5.2 AVAILABLE DATA AND DATA-COLLECTION METHODS

All modes

To follow the development of traffic and the distribution between different modes, Uppsala municipality has been conducting extensive travel surveys every fifth year since the year 2000, with the last survey conducted 2015. Since then, Uppsala has changed method to receive traffic-behaviour data more frequently. In cooperation with the Region Uppsala, the city has access to travel-data collected by the survey *Kollektivtrafikbarometern* conducted by *Svensk Kollektivtrafik*. This survey is conducted continuously throughout the year by using phone- or webb-based interviews of a representative sample of the population to produce travel-data on an annual basis.

This shift to more continuous data-collection allows to follow the development of travel-behaviour and the modal split of walking and cycling more closely than the previously used method. The annual modal-split figures and other data from the travel-survey *Kollektivtrafikbarometern* for Uppsala can therefore be seen as key indicators for following the overall development of walking and cycling in the municipality.

Bicycle traffic

Bicycle traffic is measured both with permanent and temporary counters.

Permanent counters: Currently, Uppsala uses permanent counters at **five locations** within the city boundaries. They have been installed between 2011 and 2014, with reliable count data available from 2015.

The counters on *Vårdsätravägen*, *Resecentrum* and *Islandsbron* use induction loops (see chapter 6 for a description of measuring technology). Only bicycle-traffic is measured (probably also e-scooters). The count-data they return is collected automatically and stored in the data-collecting system *Eco-Visio* by the supplier of the counters (*EcoCounter*). The minimum aggregation interval of counts is 15 minutes.

¹⁵ Uppsala kommun, 2020. Cykelåret 2020

Another counter, installed on the bicycle- and pedestrian bridge *Hamnspången* uses radar-technology which (technically) can count both passing cyclists and pedestrians and distinguish between them. The data has high temporal resolution (single passages can be identified) and also includes information on the direction of travel. Count-data is collected and stored in the data-collecting system *Infracontrol Online*.

The fifth permanent counter is installed on *Dag Hammarskölds väg*. It uses a camera-based system that counts both pedestrians and cyclists and registers travel direction. Data from this counter is exported to the data-collecting system *EdevaLive*. Raw-data consists of single-passages with a time-stamp, but the *Edeva*-system currently only allows export of aggregated data with a temporal resolution of 15 minutes¹⁶.

Temporary counts: Temporary counts have been conducted frequently, using pneumatic tube counters. Between 2015 and 2020, the municipality has conducted temporary counts at 194 locations. Counting periods are typically seven to ten days. The aggregation level is low, single passages can be identified.

The temporary counts have not been conducted based on a long-term measurement plan with reoccurring measuring locations and regular measurements. They were rather initiated ad-hoc to answer to specific needs, e.g. as input for decisions on investments or maintenance.

Additional information is stored in some cases, such as the weather-situation during the measuring period or circumstances that might have influenced the results such as traffic works. Results of temporary counts are further calibrated against data from permanent counters to take seasonal variations into account.

Data from temporary counts performed by the municipality is fed into the municipality's traffic analytics platform, *Trafficweb*¹⁷. Data from counts from 2016 and forward is stored in *Trafficweb*.

Additional to the counts conducted by the municipality, a large number of temporary measurements have been conducted during 2020 and 2021 as part of a national pilot study to develop a standardised method for estimating bicycle traffic on a national level (vehicle-kilometres). The measurements have been conducted by the Swedish Road and Transport Research Institute (VTI) and the results are available to Uppsala municipality.

In 2020, the project conducted counts of one week at 54 locations in Uppsala, in 2021 at 81 locations. Both pneumatic tube counters and camera-based systems have been used, with high temporal resolution (single passages). It is not known to this study whether the results of these counts are integrated in *Trafficweb*.

¹⁶ Tommy Eriksson, 2022, personal communication.

¹⁷ <https://trafficweb.io/>

Picture 4.1: Bicycle counting locations in Uppsala (short time, bike pilot and whole-year measurement) between 2016 and 2020.

Pedestrian traffic

Only little data on pedestrian movements across the entire city seems to be available, apart from the travel-survey results. In 2018, a larger WiFi-based measurement was done in the **central station area** in 2018, using close to 60 measurement stations.

In the **central pedestrian area**, the inner-city organisation *Citysamverkan* has 5-6 permanent measuring locations using a camera-based system¹⁸ to measure pedestrian movements with 14 cameras. The data from these stations is used to estimate the number of visitors to this area and daily, seasonal and annual variations.

Citysamverkan shares a report with measurement results with the municipality on a monthly basis. During the Covid-19 pandemic, this data was used to follow the development of activities in the pedestrian area. Apart from that, no evidence of systematic use of this information could be found.

Further, the camera-based bicycle counter on *Dag Hammarskölds väg* can count pedestrian passages. This data has been used to identify seasonal patterns in pedestrian- and bicycle traffic, but not systematically for traffic measurements.

All in all, data on pedestrian flows is scarce outside of the inner-city pedestrian area and to our knowledge currently not systematically used by the municipality.

5.3 CURRENT USE AND MANAGEMENT OF DATA

It has been difficult to thoroughly evaluate how the currently available data on bicycle- and pedestrian traffic is used in planning and in the municipalities decision-making process. Based on the results of the conducted survey and

¹⁸ Springboard, <https://www.spring-board.info/>

interviews as well as direct feedback from contact persons, some observations are presented below. It needs to be stressed that the results are based on a very limited sample and may not reflect the practices of the entire organisation. A compilation of survey-results and of interview-responses is presented in appendix 1 & 2.

The most commonly used data are the results from travel surveys (RVU), followed by data from traffic-counters.

The most common use of data is in stakeholder-involvement (medborgardialog), but also to some extent in traffic planning and evaluation of measures. However, the use of data from bicycle-flow measurements for planning and evaluation seems to be limited. In specific cases, data from temporary measurements has been used to prioritise winter-maintenance and to decide whether the construction of a segregated bicycle-path can be motivated¹⁹.

The transport section of the municipality (Trafik och samhälle) is currently responsible for pedestrian- and bicycle data. Only a few persons directly involved in bicycle traffic seem to be using that data and this limited group also seems to be the owner of the collected count-data.

Beyond this limited group, understanding of how pedestrian- and bicycle-data can be used as well as what data already is available seems to be largely lacking.

However, the data is, at least theoretically, widely available since it is stored in the traffic-data system *Trafficweb* and all municipal organisations can gain access to this system upon request. The number of registered users in *Trafficweb* is relatively high, but only few users are active. During the introduction of *Trafficweb*, efforts have been made to spread information on how to access and use data and even how specific counts can be ordered, but apparently to little avail.

Since then, little active effort seems to be made to make data accessible to others than the data-owner or to process it in such a way that it can provide valuable information to other departments or to third parties. This can at least partly be explained by lack of demand

The available data is sufficient to roughly follow the overall development of cycling in the municipality, primarily thanks to the shift to more regular travel surveys and the permanent counters. Specific requests are served ad-hoc with temporary measurements, e.g. with dedicated before-after measurements.

However, data on pedestrian- and bicycle traffic is currently not used strategically and widely throughout the organisation. The currently available data is further not deemed sufficient to understand the development of walking and cycling in the city on a more detailed level nor as a basis for strategic planning decisions.

¹⁹ Sara Andersson, Uppsala Municipality, personal communication 2022-02-17

5.4 CAPACITY FOR DATA MANAGEMENT AND PROCESSING

The municipality of Uppsala has a well-developed IT-department with high capacity to manage information systems. It has also collected considerable experience and in-house development capacity for using GIS-systems to connect location data with other information.

It is therefore deemed that Uppsala would have sufficient in-house knowledge to develop and provide an IT-infrastructure for more systematic, partly automated collection and storage of bicycle- and pedestrian-related data and to make the data more accessible. However, this would demand a dedicated effort and cooperation between the IT-department and departments that both provide or use traffic-related data.

5.5 DESIRED DATA AND ITS POTENTIAL USE

Both the conducted survey and interviews as well as the responses during the two workshops indicated an awareness of the importance of collecting data and an interest to move towards more data-driven planning.

The presented motives to collect and use bicycle and pedestrian traffic data were:

- To be able to justify investments and efforts for pedestrian and bicycle traffic
- To be able to identify and choose efficient measures
- To be able to organise maintenance efficiently
- To be able to follow up and evaluate measures (and thus build institutional knowledge for future planning)
- To be able to identify measures that can attract groups that don't cycle or walk today
- To be able to provide better safety and security, also during special events

Wishes concerning data that were expressed were:

- Detailed and comprehensive information on traffic volumes on a street-segment level
- Data on temporal variations
- Information on travel-time, speed and where congestion occurs
- Reliable data on the development of walking and cycling
- Knowledge about the current and potential users - who they are but also their motives to choose to cycle or walk or not to.

Further it was expressed that data should be available in processed form that is easily accessible and understandable. Ideally the data would be presented connected to map-data and easily accessible, with processed data presented in dashboards.

5.6 GOALS

During workshop 2, the participants were tasked to develop goals for data-collection and use in Uppsala, with a time horizon of two years. The expressed goals vary considerably, from rather operational goals – e.g. to have enough data

to inform maintenance or infrastructure improvements, to be able to produce heatmaps or to have a platform to visualise data – to more organisational goals such as creating processes and institutional maturity that allows for more data-driven decision making. Table 4.1 presents goals expressed during workshop 2.

In two years we will have access to correct and reliable data that allows us to develop our processes and organisation. (Om två år har vi tillgång till korrekt och tillförlitlig data som gör att vi kan verksamhetsutveckla)
In two years time we got enough data to do quite good priorities according to wideing, paving and removal of snow in our cycle and pedestrian infrastructure system
In two years time we have a reliable way of counting and using pedestrian and cyclist data for outdoor areas.
In two years, sensor data about our (bicycle)flows will reduce climate gas emission. (Om två år kan sensordata av våra flöden minska klimatutsläppen.)
In two years we will have a system to measure bicycle and pedestrian flows that provides additional value to our citizens in terms of accessibility, security and maintenance. (Om två år har vi ett system att mäta gc-flöden som ger mervärde för våra medborgare i termer av framkomlighet, trygghet och underhåll.)
In two years we will have a way of showing this data.
In two years we will be able to produce heat-maps that show where people move in Uppsala, both cyclists and pedestrians. (Om två år har vi möjlighet att skapa heatmaps som visar var människor rör sig i Uppsala, både cyklister och gående.)
In two years we will have an organisation that has reached a level of digital maturity that allows us to plan based on up-to date data. (Om två år har vi en organisation som har en digital mognad som gör att vi kan utveckla med hjälp av aktuell data)
In two years we will have a platform for visualising data in a way that makes it available for – everyone ? (Om två år har vi en plattform för att visualisera data så att det blir tillgängligt för... alla?)
In two years we will have developed an understanding of the value of data as a strategic resource. (Om två år förstår vi värdet av data som en strategisk resurs.)
In two years we will develop our activities based on data we collect, based on parameters such as sex, age etc. (Om två år verksamhetsutvecklar vi genom den data vi samlar in baserat på kön ålder osv..)
We have reached a certain maturity and developed processes for using data in planning and maintenance and have started to implement them. (Vi har skapat en process och mognad i vår organisation som är på väg att implementeras där vi nyttjar datan i planering och underhåll.)

Table 4.1: Goals concerning measuring bicycle and pedestrian traffic in Uppsala, expressed by the participants in workshop 2. Answers in Swedish were translated, the original answer is presented in brackets.

5.7 DISCUSSION OF UPPSALA'S SITUATION

Our impression is that the collection and use of bicycle- and pedestrian data in Uppsala is currently conducted on an **ad-hoc** basis rather than systematically and strategically.

Bicycle traffic

Within the municipal organisation, considerable knowledge about pedestrian- and bicycle-traffic in the city can doubtlessly be found. However, this knowledge seems bound to a few individuals rather than being widely available and systematically used.

The municipality has access to data on bicycle flows from a relatively large number of locations and the data from the five permanent counters is valuable to follow long-term trends and as baseline-data. The large number of temporary counts, especially for 2020 and 2021 from the VTI-measurements, can contribute with significant additional insight if used and processed systematically.

The available data is systematically stored in *Trafficweb* and the municipality also has access to and stores raw-data separately. Theoretically, access to data is good since *Trafficweb* can be used by all municipal organisations. However, understanding of the potential of the available data and awareness of the possibilities this data provides seems to be limited to a small number of individuals.

Further, *Trafficweb* currently does not contain the most valuable data on bicycling, the data from all the permanent counting stations. This data is currently transmitted to different data-collecting systems and is not accessible in a unified way.

Further, the number and location of the permanent counters does currently not allow for reliable areal-counts, e.g. cyclists entering or leaving the inner city or the city-centre. This would allow to follow the development and temporal variation of cycle traffic more reliably and to estimate the importance of bicycle-commuting, in the same way as it is done for motorised traffic through the measuring stations on the inner-city ring/*innerstadssnittet*.

Pedestrian traffic

Concerning pedestrian traffic, the availability of data is very limited and seems not to be used for planning purposes. Relatively detailed data is available for the pedestrian area in the centre through the measurements by *Citysamverkan*, but the area is small which limits the data's significance.

6 Data-collecting technologies

6.1 INTRODUCTION

There are many different methods and technologies for collecting data about cyclist- and pedestrian traffic, both traditional and emerging methods. Some methods provide specific information that cannot be gathered by other means, some are overlapping and providing the same or similar information. All methods have their specific properties, advantages and disadvantages. Picture 5.1 provides a first overview.

This chapter focuses on methods that can be used for describing the movement of cyclists and pedestrians through line-counts, areal counts or trajectories (see chapter 2.2) and excludes methods that collect accident data, qualitative information such as user-experiences or travel surveys. Emphasis is put on methods that collect data digitally and continuously. The selected methods are described in greater detail in the following chapters. In chapter 5.10, the properties of the different methods are compared and summarised.

Picture 5.1: Methods to collect data about pedestrian- and bicycle-traffic. Based on Lee & Sener, 2020), adapted by the authors.

6.2 TRADITIONAL GATE-COUNTS

Introduction

Gate-counts²⁰ of cyclists and pedestrians as well as cars have been used for decades and are the backbone of traditional traffic measuring. Also in a foreseeable future, gate counts will play a key role in measuring traffic. Available technologies for automated gate-counts of cyclists and/or pedestrian are shortly described in this chapter.

Gate-counts simply count the number of passing objects across an imaginary gate or line. Their typical outputs are the number of passages during a specific time-slot or a recording of each passage associated with a timestamp.

There are many different ways to collect gate-count traffic data. Below, common ones are listed:

- Manual counts
- Pneumatic tubes
- Inductive loops
- Piezoelectric strips
- Active infrared
- Passive infrared, pyroelectric
- Radar
- Camera-based (described in separate chapter)

Some technologies can count and differentiate between different modes, some are limited to one mode or cannot differentiate.

For the purpose of this feasibility study, focus is put on technologies that are suitable for continuous data collection with the possibility to electronically transmit measurement data. Manual counts and pneumatic tubes are typically used for temporary measurements with manual transfer of data and are not further described here. However, a repository for bicycle or pedestrian data (see chapter 7) should always also allow for the storage of data from temporary measurements.

In the following sections, a selection of sensor technologies is shortly described.

Inductive loops

Inductive loops are sensor spools installed permanently into the carriageway which create a signal when metallic objects such as a bicycle or a car pass.

Advanced induction loop counters analyse the signature of the electromagnetic signal induced by a passing vehicle and can differentiate between cars, bicycles and even e-scooters. They can measure direction of travel and roughly even speed²¹.

Since they are embedded in the street surface and operate without mechanical contact, they are durable and suitable for permanent installation. The cost of installation is relatively high due to the need to install the loops into the street surface. The loops are connected to a counter unit that processes the signal,

²⁰ See chapter 2.2. for a definition

²¹ Source: www.eco-counter.com

registers, stores and transfers measurement data. For automated data collection, this unit also needs to have the capability to transfer data, for example through the mobile phone network.

Measurement precision is high as long as vehicles pass one after the other but can diminish when several bicycles pass at the same time.

Since inductive loops register metal objects that pass, they cannot be used to measure pedestrian traffic.

*Picture 5.2: Inductive loops are permanently installed into the carriageway and can detect passing bicycles.
Source: EcoCounter*

Piezoelectric counters

Piezoelectric sensors change their electrical properties when pressure is applied. They are installed as strips perpendicular to the driving direction and can register the pressure caused by passing vehicles. Usually, two parallel sensor strips are installed at a certain distance to be able to calculate both weight, axle distance and speed of the passing vehicle. By analysing the signature of the signal, counters using piezoelectric sensors can differentiate between cars, bicycles and even e-scooters. They can measure direction of travel and roughly even speed²².

Similarly to inductive loops, the sensors are permanently installed into the road surface and are well protected. The cost of installation is relatively high due to the need to install the loops into the street surface.

Since the sensors are embedded in the street surface, they are durable and suitable for permanent installation. They need to be connected to a counter unit that processes the signal, registers, stores and transfers measurement data. For automated data collection, this unit also needs to have the capability to transfer data, for example through the mobile phone network.

Measurement precision is high as long as vehicles pass one after the other but can diminish when several bicycles pass at the same time.

Pedestrians cannot easily be registered by piezoelectric sensors, at least as long as they are narrow strips, since it cannot be ensured that a pedestrian sets his

²² Source: www.metrocount.com

foot on the sensor when passing. For measuring pedestrian traffic, larger piezoelectric pads would be required, which would make installation costly²³

Picture 5.3: Piezoelectric counters are permanently installed into the carriageway and can detect passing vehicles. Advanced systems can determine axle-distance, direction of travel and speed. Source: Metrocount.

Active infrared, infrared beam counters

Infrared beam counters are a simple counting method where a constant infrared beam is sent from a transmitter to a receiver that is installed across the measuring gate. When an object passes through, the beam is interrupted and a data logger registers the count. Single beam counters cannot measure the direction of travel of passing objects. However, some counters use double beams to register the direction of travel.

Active infrared counters are relatively easy and cheap to set up and are commonly used in indoors environments. However, their accuracy can be affected by outdoor environments, such as wind and rain. They can have high levels of error if several objects such as groups of pedestrians or cyclists pass at the same time²⁴. In most cases, the count data is manually read or extracted from the measuring unit. For automated data collection, this unit also needs to have the capability to transfer data.

Infrared beam counters cannot differentiate between pedestrians or bicycles.

Passive infrared, pyroelectric

Passive infrared or pyroelectric devices detect pedestrians and cyclists by reacting to their bodyheat. The passive infrared sensor is installed at one side of the counting "gate" and compares the temperature of the background to the heat patterns/infrared radiation emitted by passing objects. Passive infrared counters cannot measure the direction of travel of passing objects.

Passive infrared counters are relatively easy and cheap to install since only one sensor needs to be set up. They have high accuracy when persons pass one by one but errors may occur with groups or when people linger within the sensor range. Further, extreme temperatures can influence accuracy.

²³ Source: K.Ozbay et al., 2010: Automatic Pedestrian Counter. Final Report. Rutgers University and

²⁴ Eron Ozan et al., 2021: State-of-the-Art approaches to Bicycle and Pedestrian Counters. North Carolina Department of Transport, report FHWA/NC/2020-39 and Kaan Ozbay et al., 2010: Automatic Pedestrian Counter. Rutgers University

Passive infrared counters cannot differentiate between pedestrians or bicycles. They are therefore sometimes combined with sensors that can only detect bicycles such as inductive loops or piezoelectric strips. In these combination devices, the pedestrian count is calculated by subtracting the bicycle count from the total user count measured with the passive infrared sensor²⁵.

For automated data collection, the measurement unit needs to have the capability to transfer data, for example through the mobile phone network.

Radar

Radar technology can be used to measure cyclists and pedestrians, using an integrated microwave transmitter and antenna and processing of the reflected signal. Radar sensors can measure the direction of travel and the speed of passing objects and most radar counters can differentiate between cyclists and pedestrians.

The measurement unit is typically installed roughly perpendicular to the travel direction and at a certain height. Radar counters are relatively easy to install since they can be mounted on a pole or existing lamppost. No information has been found concerning accuracy, but it is judged to be at least as high as other methods.

For automated data collection, the measurement unit needs to have the capability to transfer data, for example through the mobile phone network.

Picture 5.4 (left): Radar-counter at a dutch cycle-path. Source: Cycledata.nl

Picture 5.5 (right): Radar-counter at a cycle-path in Ashburn, USA. Source: roadsysllc.com

Camera-based systems

Camera-based systems with picture processing technology can be used for gate-measurements. This technology is described in a separate chapter.

Conclusions

Gate-counts, especially if they are performed continuously, are currently the most precise and reliable method to measure cycle- and pedestrian volumes over

²⁵ Ryus, P., et al., 2014: Methods and Technologies for Pedestrian and Bicycle Volume Data Collection. *Methods and Technologies for Pedestrian and Bicycle Volume Data Collection*. <https://doi.org/10.17226/23429>

time at a given location. In a foreseeable future, they will remain necessary, at least to provide reliable reference values for other measuring technologies.

There are many well-proven sensor-technologies for gate-counts of cyclists and pedestrians. Which solution is most suitable depends on the specific demands for each measurement site and what data is required. At some locations, the possibility to detect the travel direction or to differentiate between cyclists and pedestrians might be crucial, at others not. What technology should be chosen ultimately depends on finding an acceptable balance between investment costs, installation and operational cost and the accuracy and reliability of results. For a detailed comparison of measuring technologies, the *Guidebook on Pedestrian and Bicycle Volume Data Collection*²⁶ is recommended (The guidebook lacks information on radar-based equipment.)

No matter what counting technology is used, the way data is aggregated, stored and transferred is important to consider. For permanent counting stations, automated transfer of data, e.g. through the mobile phone network or other channels is highly recommended, ideally in real-time or several times per day. Further, the data extracted from the measuring device should be as little aggregated as possible. Ideally the data is extracted and stored with a separate entry for each count, including time-information and if available, additional information such as mode or direction. In that way, the desired level of aggregation can be chosen freely at a later time and is not predetermined by the measuring equipment.

Table 5.1 provides a rough overview of the properties of the presented measuring technologies for gate-counts, with rough classifications of accuracy and cost.

	Counts cyclists	Counts pedestrians	Differentiates ped./cyclist	Precision	Direction of travel	Speed	Cost of installation	Cost of equipment	Temporary/Permanent
Manual	X	X	X	***	X	-	*	*** (staff)	T
Pneumatic tubes	X	-	-	**	?	-	*	**	T
Inductive loops	X	-	-	**	X	**	***	**	P
Piezo	X	-	-	**	X	**	***	**	P
Active IR	X	X	-	**	-	-	*	*	T, P
Passive IR	X	X	-	**	-	-	*	**	T, P
Radar	X	X	X	**	X	***	*	***	T, P
Camera	X	X	X	Varies	X	**	**	***	T, P

Table 5.1: Overview over presented sensor-technologies for measuring bicycle and pedestrian traffic.

²⁶ Ryus, P., Ferguson, E., Laustsen, K. M., Schneider, R. J., Proulx, F. R., Hull, T., & Miranda-Moreno, L. (2014). *Guidebook on Pedestrian and Bicycle Volume Data Collection*. UC Berkeley: Safe Transportation Research & Education Center.

6.3 CAMERA-BASED SYSTEMS

Introduction

Camera-based systems measure traffic by means of computer-based analysis of video-footage. Similarly to human vision, computer-algorithms can detect objects in the picture, categorise them and also follow their movement and count them. The dramatic increase in available and affordable computing power and the advent of artificial intelligence and machine learning have made sophisticated picture-analysis possible. For traffic measurements, typically a road-section or a junction is filmed from above and at an angle by one or several fixed or temporary cameras. The footage is then analysed by computer-vision software, identifying the movement of people or vehicles. Once an object has been identified, the software can follow and record its trace through the recorded section. Through different attributes like size, proportions and others, the analysing software can determine the traffic mode of the recorded object. Most systems can differentiate between cars, trucks, cyclists and pedestrians. Picture 5.6 shows an example of object-recognition and how different vehicles and persons moving through the filmed intersection are traced.

Picture 5.6: Still-picture from a camera-based traffic measurement system overlooking an intersection in Stockholm. The software can identify moving objects and creates a shape representing the moving object. A traffic mode is attributed to each object based on certain parameters, e.g. footprint, form etc. The movement of each object through the picture-frame is traced, illustrated by a line. Normally, only the abstract frames and their trajectory are stored, not the background-picture. Here it is included for illustration purposes. Source: Viscando.

Once the moving objects have been categorized and their trace recorded, traffic flow can be measured by applying virtual “counting-gates” or counting-lines, as illustrated in picture 5.7.

Picture 5.7: Still-picture from a camera-based traffic measurement system overlooking a road section in Prague. Virtual counting-gates or counting-lines can be defined, named A, B, C and D in the picture. Objects crossing the gates are counted according to their category. The recorded figures represent the number of each category that has passed so far during the measuring day. Source: GoodVision

A typical field of vision is around 25x25 metres, but this can vary significantly based on both location, camera resolution and the systems computing capacity. Counting-lines can be defined at will within the recorded field of vision. In systems where the complete trajectory-data is stored, also post-recording measurements with changed or additional counting lines are possible.

Advanced systems have the capability to measure a large number of moving objects simultaneously which makes them suitable for situations where large flows can occur or where objects move in crowds, a situation where traditional gate-counting methods often fail. Pictures 5.8-5.10 illustrate situations where reliable counts with traditional gate-measuring methods could be challenging.

Pictures 5.8, 5.9 and 5.10: Examples of measuring-situation with groups of cyclists or pedestrians where traditional counting-methods would be challenged. Above-left: Dense groups of cyclists passing an intersection during bicycle-event Vätternrundan. Source: Viscando. Above-right: A group of pedestrians crossing the streets in Warsaw. Source: GoodVision. Below: Gathering of people in connection to a festival, counted from video-footage recorded by drones. Source: Data from Sky.

Collected data can be stored locally which demands manual collection or transferred wirelessly, usually to a service provided by the manufacturer from which data is provided to the customer.

Collected data

Compared to traditional gate-counting methods, camera-based system can collect a far richer set of data. They can measure several objects simultaneously, differentiate between traffic modes and provide gate-count data for each mode. Counts can be conducted through one or several virtual gates/lines defined in the picture-frame, with exact time-stamps or aggregated. This allows for example for simultaneous counting of traffic on a car-lane, a parallel cycle lane and a sidewalk, with mode-differentiation for each lane. Counts can further be differentiated by direction of movement.

For each recorded object, its velocity can be calculated. This allows to measure the average speed as well as the distribution of speed of passing vehicles or whether speed differs between different times of the day.

More advanced systems can record exact trajectories of each object through the filmed area with the precision of decimetres. This allows to analyse exact route choice patterns, e.g. how many pedestrians walk on the bicycle-lane, what shortcuts are taken or to estimate waiting times. Further, this allows for analysis and quantification of route-choices in intersections. Data collected through advanced camera-based systems can thus provide very detailed information on the traffic-movements in street sections or intersections. This data can also be used for calibrating traffic models.

Camera-based systems can further provide instantaneous counts of the number of vehicles or people within the filmed area as well as their speed, which can be used to control crowding or congestion.

The precision of counts, identification of different traffic modes and the spatial precision possible depends on both the resolution and light-sensitivity of the

used camera, its placement and how advanced the used picture-analysis software is. Some system use two cameras for stereoscopic vision for higher precision in mode-recognition.

System solutions and their differences, privacy

On-site or off-site processing: Camera-based systems can be divided in two groups based on whether the processing of the video-image is performed on-site or not.

In systems that process video-pictures to data directly **on-site**, the video-footage is transformed to abstract, non-identifiable object-frames and trajectories directly in the measuring system. No video-signals are usually recorded, only information on the vehicle category, trajectories and time-data leaves the system for storage and further analysis. Since none of the video-footage leaves the system, it cannot be used to identify individuals. Camera-equipment, a processing unit and technology for data storage and -transfer are all installed at the measuring site and are usually provided as an integrated system. Examples for measuring-systems that process data on site are *Viscando Otus3D*, *Telraam*, *Numina* and *EcoCounter Citix*. Since these systems do not record any video-footage, no permissions for camera-surveillance should be needed and no privacy issues emerge.

The user purchases or hires the necessary hardware from the provider. Analysis of data and presentation of results is usually offered as a service by the provider, either on a subscription or case-by-case basis.

In systems with **off-site** analysis, the picture-analysis occurs at a different location than the recording. They are fundamentally software-services that can be fed with live or recorded video-streams from any location. They have the advantage that existing cameras can be used and transformed into traffic sensors and that the user has a free choice of camera technology. If recorded video is used, the analysis can be performed at any chosen time.

The equipment at the measuring site is usually cheaper and smaller since no processing-capacity is necessary. Further, off-site processing can allow for more advanced computer-equipment and power-supply is less problematic. Improvements and updates of the used software and algorithms have an immediate effect since data-processing is centralised. The user provides video-footage which can be live or recorded, no hardware needs to be purchased if an existing camera can be used. The analysis is purchased as a service from the provider, on a per-case, per hour or prescription basis.

The main drawback is that actual video-footage is recorded and transmitted which can raise privacy issues and demand permission for setting up surveillance cameras. Further, the camera equipment and processing-software might not be as optimised for each other as in systems that are integrated.

Examples of systems with off-site processing are *GoodVision* and *Data from Sky*.

Camera quality, weather protection and data-transfer

The resolution, field of vision and light sensitivity of the system's camera influences the detection quality and whether it can measure under poor lighting conditions. These parameters can vary significantly between different systems and need to be considered when choosing a system.

Most systems use cameras that are mounted above the street, for example on existing lamp-poles. This demands that they are designed for permanent outdoor-use, can withstand adverse weather and temperatures. Permanent installations also need a fixed power supply, for temporary measurements batteries can be used. An exception is the Belgian *Telraam*-system which is a low-cost system designed to be mounted indoors, inside a window that overlooks the street that should be observed. It requires access to an existing WiFi-network for data-transmission and has limited light-sensitivity, restricting it to counts during daytime²⁷.

Pictures 5.11 and 5.12: Left: Examples of a pole-mounted camera-based measuring system installed on a lighting pole, overlooking a street-section. Source: Viscando. Right: The low-cost camera-based measuring system Telraam is installed indoors, in private homes at windows overlooking a street.

Examples of use

Camera-based measurement systems are increasingly used for traffic measurement, primarily as advanced gate-counters but also to gather data on intersections to calibrate traffic models or for crowd-control.

In Sweden, the cities of Linköping, Huddinge and Gothenburg use permanent camera-based systems for multi-modal traffic counts. Stockholm monitors pedestrian flows in the inner city by using 14 camera-based systems to create a ring for gate- and areal-counts.

The high counting precision and resolution of advanced video-based measuring systems has also been used in several research project, e.g. during the cycle-event *Vätternrundan* where the trajectories of over 20 000 cyclists through selected intersections were recorded during one day for detailed analysis²⁸.

The low-cost *Telraam*-system is frequently used for crowd-sourced traffic counting, mainly in Belgium and the Netherlands. Municipalities provide measuring systems to interested inhabitants who can install them to conduct traffic counts from their windows. At the time of writing, over 1 600 systems are in use. The highest density can be found in the city of Leuven (Belgium) with measuring systems at over 50 street sections²⁹.

²⁷ <https://telraam.net/en>

²⁸ Michael Koucky, Alex Spielhaupter, Jacob Thåqvist, 2021: Cykelsäkerhet: Cyklisters beteende vid omledningar, avspärningar och trängsel - Vätternrundan 2019 som testbädd. Trafikverkets Skyltfonds & Folksam.

²⁹ <https://telraam.net/en>

Camera-based systems are further used to measure bicycle-traffic in Copenhagen at 20 locations and to count pedestrian at squares and in streets in Amsterdam within the city's programme to manage crowding.

Conclusions

Camera-based measuring systems offer significant advantages compared to traditional methods for gate-counting – they can differentiate between modes, reliably count also large groups and provide additional information such as trajectories or speed. Strategically placed, e.g. when overlooking an intersection, a camera-based system can measure traffic flows at several counting gates.

The cost for camera-based systems has started to become competitive to other gate-counting methods, especially if several traffic modes need to be counted simultaneously³⁰. Since the cost of computing power and hardware can be expected to continue to fall, measuring methods based on picture-analysis are therefore expected to become more and more competitive and to replace more traditional measuring methods. However, as many providers have a business model that includes services such as data-collection and processing, the cost-structure for permanent measurements might shift from investment-costs to recurring subscription fees, something that needs to be considered in economic comparisons.

If relatively large flows of pedestrians should be counted with high spatial precision or in mixed-mode environments, there are basically no alternatives to camera-based systems currently available.

Systems with on-site picture processing cause no privacy concern since video-footage is neither stored nor transmitted. However, they might still cause negative reactions from the public since visible cameras are installed and can be interpreted as surveillance.

Systems with off-site picture processing, where video-footage is transmitted or stored, might cause privacy-concerns and require permission to be installed. Therefore, the legal framework as well as the public acceptance needs to be examined before such systems are considered.

Camera-based measuring systems provide many advantages compared to more traditional methods. It is therefore clearly recommended to consider such methods whenever traffic counts are necessary, both for motor vehicles, bicycles or pedestrians. The possibility to measure different traffic modes simultaneously opens considerable opportunities for synergies and cost-reduction and can provide additional information on bicycle- and pedestrian flows at little cost when it is combined with motor-vehicle measurements. For reliable counts of pedestrian traffic in situations where high flows can be expected or to measure crowding, camera-based systems are one of the few available options.

³⁰ A. Singh, Viscando, direct communication, 2021-12-20.

6.4 SHORT-RANGE ANTENNA-BASED (WIFI, BLUETOOTH)

Introduction

Almost all mobile phones today have the capability to connect to local networks or devices wirelessly through WiFi- or Bluetooth-signals. A phone with WiFi or Bluetooth activated that passes a corresponding sensor (with WiFi or Bluetooth antenna) can be detected and registered. The typical range a sensor can cover is 25 up to 100 meters. This can provide counts of the number of phones within the detection zone. Strategically placed, a single sensor can thus be used as an automated counting system for gate-counts, for example registering phones entering a certain road or building. Further, the number of devices within the measuring range can be counted, providing an instant areal count.

Each mobile phone has a unique identifier (MAC – media access control address) that can be registered when the phone is detected by a nearby sensor.

Thanks to the possibility to identify the passing phones by their MAC-address, additional opportunities emerge. Using only one sensor, it can be measured how long time the device was within the range of the sensor or if the same device visits the measuring area repeatedly and when.

By using multiple sensors with known locations in an array, trajectories can be estimated as the presence and time of a phone moving through the area is picked up by one sensor at the time. The spatial resolution is in such a case determined by the density of sensors. If the sensors are placed so close to each other that a phone can be detected by several sensor simultaneously, the location can be estimated with even greater precision by triangulation, based on the recorded signal strength at each sensor.

Multiple-sensor arrangements can thus be used to study where people walk and how long they stay at certain locations to understand flow- and behaviour patterns or to create origin-destination matrices.

The number of sensors needed, and therefore also the cost of measuring, is determined by the area that should be covered and the desired spatial resolution and grows quickly with areal size.

Since detection is based on an active exchange of information between the mobile phone and the sensor rather than a physical measurement, it takes a certain time. Signal discovery time of WiFi is around one second, Bluetooth can require as much as ten seconds. This implies that the method is primarily suitable to detect slowly moving objects such as pedestrians (Bluetooth and WiFi) or cyclists (WiFi) carrying a phone.

Sensors can be deployed temporarily, e.g. during a measuring campaign, or be installed permanently. Even existing WiFi-access-points can potentially be used as sensors, if access is granted.

Collected data and privacy

The data collected by the sensor is the presence of a specific phone within the range of the sensor, the corresponding time, signal strength and the device's unique MAC-address. The temporal resolution is very high. The spatial

information is based on the known location of the sensors. Its precision is dependent on the density of sensors within the measurement area.

The registered MAC-address is unique for each phone. Even if the identity of the user cannot be determined directly from it, recorded data and trajectories containing MAC-addresses raise considerable privacy issues. The Swedish Authority for Privacy Protection (*Integritetskyddsmyndigheten*, formerly *Dataskyddinspektionen*) ruled therefore in 2015 that full MAC-addresses should be considered personal data that cannot be collected and stored without consent under Swedish law³¹.

Since full MAC-addresses therefore cannot legally be stored, exact trajectories of individuals are not possible to record legally. To still be able to legally extract relevant information from WiFi-measurements, Bumble Labs, a Swedish provider of WiFi-based measuring services, has developed methods based on so called statistical fingerprinting that only uses parts of the phones MAC-address³². This allows to identify the intensity of traffic between measuring spots without the possibility to identify the trajectories of individuals.

Representativeness and reliability of results

Antenna-based systems can reliably measure the presence of a mobile phone, given that it is detectable. Only the presence of persons with a phone with activated WiFi or Bluetooth-functionality can be recorded. Mobile phones are basically ubiquitous in Sweden and an overwhelming majority of phones has WiFi and Bluetooth capability. This implies that the measured data can be assumed to be representative of the population at large, with the exception of young children. It can further be expected that most people have WiFi and Bluetooth activated, but not all. Count- or flow-data from WiFi-based measuring systems should therefore ideally be calibrated with occasional counts with other methods.

Since the method only measures the presence of mobile phones and no other information is available, it cannot discriminate between cyclists and pedestrians. It should therefore preferably be used in situations where the mode of travel is given, e.g. in pedestrian areas or in indoor environments, or for measurement where the distinction is irrelevant.

Examples of use

Short-range antenna-based measurements have been used to study the movements of pedestrians and in shops, airports as well as in limited inner-city areas. Further, the technology has been used for counts along hiking and bicycle routes such as touristic trails, both for counts and to estimate trip length and dwelling time. They are further suitable to estimate the number of persons present at events or in buildings.

Several studies have been conducted in central areas of Swedish cities, for example in Västerås³³ and Gothenburg. Pictures 5.13 and 5.14 illustrate the

³¹ SOU, 2016: Hur står det till med den personliga integriteten? En kartläggning av Integritetskommittén. Statens offentliga utredningar, SOU 2016:41. 1

³² <https://etn.se/index.php/reportage/68290-mater-flodet-i-butiker-och-pa-kontor.html>

³³ <https://fastighetstidningen.se/den-nya%E2%80%A8-matbara-staden/>

network of temporary sensors used to measure and analyse the movement of pedestrians in the most central part of Gothenburg. In this measuring campaign performed by Bumbee Labs, 50 temporary sensors were deployed on an area of roughly one square kilometre and over two million passages were recorded during five days³⁴. Each sensor had a detection radius of roughly 25 meters and recorded each phone (with WiFi turned on) within that range. During the five-day measuring campaign, roughly two million passages were recorded by the sensors

Pictures 5.13 and 5.14: Left: Location of the 50 sensors during a five-day measurement campaign in Gothenburg using WiFi-sensors. The colour indicates the average number of recorded passages for each sensor. Right: The relative importance of flows between different sensor-locations is illustrated by colour, where red implies highest flows. Observe that the exact route choice not always can be extracted, the link simply indicates that people have moved from one to another measuring area. Source: Göteborgs Stad, 2019.

The number of passages at each measuring point, main connections for pedestrian traffic as well as the temporal changes and differences between weekdays and weekends could be extracted from the measurements.

Also the inner-city association of Uppsala has performed pedestrian measurements, probably using WiFi-tracking technology.

Conclusions

With measurements based on WiFi-sensors, the travel mode cannot be determined. Their use is therefore limited to measurements in which the travel mode is of little interest or to areas that are only (or predominantly) frequented by pedestrians, such as pedestrian zones. Within these limitations, WiFi-based measurements can provide insight into pedestrian traffic and can be a valuable source of information for inner-city development.

Since WiFi-sensors can measure large flows of people passing through “measuring fields” of 50 meters or more in diameter, they are also suitable if the number of visitors at a certain location, e.g. a square, or at a specific event should be counted.

A grid of WiFi-sensors is an efficient method to gather information of the numbers and movements of people in a pedestrian zone. The high temporal resolution allows for analysis of when peak-flows occur or how pedestrian movement vary within or between days or seasons. For a detailed analysis of pedestrian travel patterns in an area, the density of sensors needs to be high. The

³⁴ Göteborgs Stad, 2019: WiFi-mätningar av fotgängarflöden i Göteborgs innerstad – slutrapport. Trafikkontoret, Dnr 5799/18

number of necessary sensors – and the corresponding costs - basically grows exponentially with the size of the area and with the desired spatial resolution. The method is thus mainly suitable for relatively small areas, for larger areas, cost can become prohibitive.

However, if already existing WiFi-antennas can be accessed and utilised (e.g. WiFi hotspots), the cost of measurement can potentially be reduced. This option demands cooperation between the collector of data and the owners of the antennas as well as standardised access protocols. If successful, this could make a measuring grid for continuous measuring feasible at relatively low cost, which would open for a more widespread adoption of the method.

In Uppsala, *Uppsala Citysamverkan AB* – a platform for inner-city business – operates a free WiFi-service with outdoor coverage in the central parts of Uppsala³⁵. The antennas of this network could potentially provide a basis for a WiFi-based measuring system.

Data-collection through WiFi-networks and the interpretation of results demands significant know-how in IT as well as data-processing capability. This is further enhanced by the limitations imposed by Swedish privacy legislation which bans the direct use of the full MAC-addresses. This adds complexity to data-collection and analysis since methods like statistical fingerprinting need to be applied to stay within the boundaries of the law. Municipalities can therefore not expect to be able to conduct WiFi-based measurements on their own nor to get access to detailed raw-data. Currently, only one provider - Bumble Labs - is known to have the capability to collect and process WiFi-based position data in accordance with Swedish privacy legislation. This creates a risk of dependency on a single supplier of data and a vulnerability if this supplier changes its business model or ceases to exist. Therefore, a municipality should avoid to solely rely on data or indicators based on WiFi- measurements in its decision processes but also use redundant data-sources.

Detailed data on pedestrian movements can have a significant value for business development and localization-analysis. The cost of collecting this data could therefore potentially be shared with local businesses or city-district associations. *Uppsala Citysamverkan AB* already measures customer flows and could be a potential partner for a permanent network of sensors – especially if their existing WiFi-antennas could be used.

6.5 LOCAL APP-BASED TRACKING

Introduction

Bicycle- and even pedestrian trajectories can be collected by dedicated smartphone applications that are installed by users who are ready to willingly share their route information. These tracking apps are usually distributed and marketed by public agencies or research organisations with the goal to collect travel behaviour data and to promote cycling. The apps collect GPS-traces of the users' trips and often also additional information such as demographic

³⁵ <http://www.uppsalawifi.se/>

information, trip purpose, rider type etc. This data is sent to a server by the user's phone, usually after each completed trip.

Users actively download the app, provide information on themselves and, in most cases, actively need to start and conclude tracking of a trip. Since the users themselves agree on sharing their tracks and the provided information and the terms of use, legal privacy issues are limited.

Picture 5.15: Screenshots of the Cycle Tracks application, developed in 2009 by the San Francisco County Transport Authority. Cycle Tracks was one of the first apps specifically designed to collect route-data from cyclists for planning use.³⁶

Collected data

The collected track-data provides information with high temporal and spatial resolution. Raw GPS trajectory points can be transformed into the desired format for nearly any type of analysis, for example to analyse route choice, travel speed distribution, the intensity of usage of infrastructure etc. If also demographic data or the category of trips is collected, additional information can be extracted.

However, raw GPS-data needs to be processed before use – the dataset can contain outliers or data that are not relevant, for example if the user has forgotten to turn off tracking after the trip was concluded. The spatial precision of GPS-data is high (around 5 metres in good conditions) but can vary depending on local circumstances. It is in any case rarely precise enough to directly aggregate trajectories or to assign them to a specific infrastructure, as illustrated in pictures 5.16 and 5.17.

³⁶ Source: Billy Charlton et al., 2010: Bicycle Route Choice Data Collection using GPS-Enabled Smartphones. Presentation submitted to the Transport Research Board Annual Meeting 2011

Pictures 5.16 and 5.17: Unprocessed GPS-tracks from cyclists from a research project in Ljubljana. The tracks in the left picture are scattered because the high density of tall buildings reduces the precision of GPS-measurements. The right picture show GPS-tracks in an open park area where the GPS-signals are undisturbed and the measured tracks more concentrated. Source: Tominc et al. 2012³⁷

Instead, tracks within a certain corridor usually need to be assigned (locked) to a wanted geometry (e.g. a street, a cycle track or an intersection) to allow for further analysis, e.g. of the number of recorded trips on that section. Processing GPS-data can therefore demand heavy computational work.

The value of recorded trajectory data and what kind of questions that can be reliably answered is further highly dependent on the **number of tracks** recorded. For detailed analysis of the properties a specific route, e.g. to better understand travel speeds, waiting times or the impact of an intervention along that route, only relatively few tracks that are analysed are necessary. However, to be able to extract reliable information on travel patterns across a larger area or the frequency of use of roads, the demands on the number of recorded tracks is significantly higher.

Examples of use

The San Francisco County Transport Authority pioneered the use of dedicated apps to collect GPS-tracks from cyclists when it launched its *Cycle Track* app in 2009. During its launch period between November 2009 and April 2010, 1 083 users downloaded the app and 7 097 trips were recorded. The data was used to analyse use-patterns and was also used as input to the local traffic model. The app was designed as open-source software and local variants have since been used in several US-cities.

In the Netherlands, GPS-trajectories of cyclists have been recorded regularly on a national level since 2015 during an annual Bicycle Count Week, using a dedicated app (*Fiets Telweek*³⁸). In both 2015 and 2016, almost 50 000 persons participated in the Bicycle Count Week. Since 2017, tracks can also be collected throughout the whole year, even if the concentrated collection-week remains. The data is used to better understand local and regional travel patterns and the distribution of cycling both temporarily and geographically.

³⁷ Biba Tominc et al., 2012: CyCity: Ljubljana Cyclists' route choice and preferences. Research report within the Swedish research programme CyCity

³⁸ <https://fietsstelweek.nl/>

Picture 5.18: Heat-map of the tracks recorded during the FietsTelweek 2016 in the Netherlands, where red indicates where most tracks were recorded. Recorded tracks are concentrated to population centres which would be expected. By normalising the recorded cycling levels with population density, the level of cycling at different locations could be estimated. However, differences can also be the result differences in the uptake of the measuring campaign in different locations. Source: FietsTelweek

The *BikeCitizen*-app³⁹ is a tracking-app that provides the user with an advanced bicycle map. The app can be used for gamification campaigns and communication with cyclists, e.g. by offering rewards or prizes after the cyclist collected a certain number of kilometres. The app has been used in campaigns and for data-collection in several large cities, mainly in Austria and Germany (Vienna, Berlin, Hamburg etc.). In Vienna alone, over 40 000 trajectories annually have been recorded with the app since 2015. The city uses the application primarily as a campaign and communication tool, but also uses the data to better understand the distribution of cycle traffic and the preferences of users.

A product similar to *BikeCitizens* is *GéoVelo*⁴⁰ that has been used in campaigns in several French cities.

Picture 5.19: Heat map of bicycle trajectories in Berlin collected by the app *BikeCitizen*, where lighter lines represent a higher concentration of recorded tracks. The heat map is based on trajectories of 113 000 trips during 2015. Note that whilst an impressive number of trips, the recorded tracks only represent a minor fraction of cycle traffic in Berlin. Source: Bike Cizen

³⁹ <https://www.bikecitizens.net/>.

⁴⁰ <https://geovelo.fr/application/>

Recruitment and motivation

To be able to collect data with dedicated tracking apps, users need to be recruited and motivated to participate which can be challenging. Motivation needs to be twofold: Firstly, to download and install the chosen app and to agree to provide information and trajectory-data to the city. Secondly, to actually activate the app during cycling trips. To reduce the burden of activation, some apps automatically record when movements are noticed, but this is more battery-draining and demands more post-processing for the extraction of bicycle trips since all trips are recorded.

When the San Francisco County Transport Authority launched its Cycle Track app in 2009, participation was entirely voluntary and not rewarded, apart from that the users could see their recorded tracks in their phone. Participation was therefore mainly motivated by contributing to improved cycle planning. While the app can be considered a success and provided valuable information, the number of participating cyclists and number of recorded tracks were very small compared to the number of cyclists and cycle trips in the region

To increase the use of tracking apps, some products have included advanced bicycle maps and reward-features to motivate their use. Examples are the apps from *BikeCitizens* and *GéoVelo*⁴¹ that are marketed towards cyclists as advanced route-planners and cycle-maps that also allows users to record information on their cycling-levels, total distance cycled, average speed or calory-use. Both applications can also include reward-systems and elements of gamification where users collect “points” while cycling with the app activated that can be exchanged against various rewards offered by a city or other partners. Using this reward system, the *BikeCizens*-app has also been used by cities as a marketing tool for cycling.

Another approach are targeted campaigns where participants are encouraged to track their trips during a limited period. In the Netherlands, the annual Bicycle Count Week (Fiets Telweek⁴²) is promoted in a national marketing campaign, including radio and TV commercials, online advertising, social media, banners, news articles and more. Cyclists are encouraged to participate, download the app and track all their cycled routes during the study period. To motivate participation, the campaign communicates that the participants contribute to the development of improved cycle infrastructure and the app provides information on cycled kilometres and burned calories during the campaign. Further, participants take part in a lottery with cycling-related prizes such as raingear, navigation-devices or electric bikes. The Dutch Bicycle Count Week has been arranged annually since 2015.

Representativeness and reliability of results

Even if a high number of trajectories is collected in a city using tracking apps, they will most probably only represent a minor fraction of all cycle- (or walking) trips in the city. To analyse travel speed or waiting times along a certain route, this is not a problem, as long as enough trajectories along that route are available. However, if information on route-choices or the intensity of use of

⁴¹ <https://geovelo.fr>, <https://www.bikecitizens.net/>

⁴² <https://fietsstelweek.nl/>

infrastructure within the entire network should be extracted, this can be of concern.

Concerning representativeness of the results, two aspects need to be considered: the representativeness of the participants as well as which trips are recorded. Users of the tracking-app are not necessarily representative for all cyclists. Further, cyclists don't necessarily record all of their trips. Schnötzlinger, Brezina and Emberger (2021)⁴³ analysed over 40 000 cycle-trajectories from Vienna that were recorded using the *BikeCitizen*-app and compared it with results from travel surveys. The analysis showed that short bicycle trips were underreported in the app-data, indicating that users mainly activated the app for longer trips.

In the same study, trajectory data was compared to results from automated counting stations in the city. The number of recorded GPS-tracks at the counting stations represented between 0.16‰ to 2.52‰ of the actual passages, with a median of 0.98‰. This implies that, on average, only about one of thousand passages were recorded by the app. The number of passages recorded by the app correlated relatively well with the data from the counting stations and the correlation was highest where cycle volumes were high. Theoretically, results from GPS-tracking could therefore be extrapolated to a larger network using data from permanent counting stations as reference points. However, the number of GPS-tracks at the reference points would need to be far higher than around 1‰ of actual passages to produce reliable results. Due to their currently small numbers, already minor deviations can significantly influence the results. This is especially true for road sections with small numbers of recorded GPS-tracks.

The authors conclude that the collected GPS-data cannot yet be used to replace conventional survey or counting methods, but that GPS-track data can provide additional value for transport planning when used to supplement traditional methods.

Conclusions

Tracking-apps that are specifically designed to collect trajectories from users that use the app voluntarily can be a valuable tool to collect data on cycling in a city. Since the users provide the data willingly and agree upon that their trajectory-data is used, privacy issues are reduced but not fully eliminated. The advantage of using dedicated applications promoted by the city compared to fitness-apps is that the city can get better access to detailed data, ensure the users what their data is used for and that it can influence what users are recruited. In most cases, also background information on the users and category of trips can be collected. This allows for more detailed analysis as well as for a better understanding of possible biases in the group of respondents.

To be useful, dedicated tracking apps need to have as many users as possible within the area and time of interest. Recruiting and promotion therefore must be an important part of any measuring campaign using dedicated tracking apps.

⁴³ Patrik Schnötzlinger, Tadej Brezina, Günter Emberger, 2021: Volunteered mass cycling self-tracking data – grade of representation and aptitude for planning. TRANSPORTMETRICA A: TRANSPORT SCIENCE

This can be achieved by intensive recruitment campaigns during a short period to motivate as many participants as possible to join and track their trips during that time, as in the dutch example of FietsTelweek (bike-counting week). Alternatively, the app offers some benefit to the user or other motivators for its use so that it is used regularly, such as contests or gamification elements. Recruiting many participants for a short period of measurement has the advantage that it is more likely that the sample is representative for a wider population.

Most information can be extracted from tracking-data if the raw GPS-trajectories are available. Therefore, cities that use tracking app data should ideally ensure to have access to this data in unprocessed form. However, processing of raw-data from GPS-tracking demands specialised skills not necessarily available within an administration and can be both time and resource consuming. Data-processing is therefore often performed by the provider of the chosen application. If this is the case, the city needs to clearly define its needs and demands on what data is desired before choosing a provider. The processing steps and the quality of the delivered data should be well documented.

GPS-trajectories are rich in information and for a detailed analysis of a specific route or a limited area, the number of necessary trajectories to allow for relevant results is limited. Examples are studies on the speed and waiting times along a specific route or studies on the change of route choices due to infrastructure changes, e.g. what alternative routes are chosen when a road is closed during roadworks or how travel speed changes depending on road conditions. For this type of studies, data from tracking apps and targeted recruitment of regular users of the route in question can provide valuable insight.

For analysis of city-wide bicycle traffic patterns, the necessary number of recorded tracks to allow for reliable results is significantly higher and can be hard to achieve. Care should therefore be taken when interpreting the results. Planning decisions should at present not be based on trajectory data only.

Despite its limitations, data from tracking apps can provide valuable insight and supplement other measurement-methods, especially if their results are combined. If a large number of trajectories can be collected and the data can successfully be calibrated against reliable bicycle count data at specific locations, it could be possible to roughly estimate both the distribution and annual volumes of bicycle traffic on a street-segment level, at least for segments with high flows. This can be used to assess where bicycle infrastructure is most used or needed as well as to identify suitable locations for bicycle volume counting.

6.6 FITNESS-APP-BASED TRACKING

Introduction

Fitness-tracking apps and devices are designed to collect and store information on the user's physical activities such as walking, running or cycling. The users record information on their fitness activities to get feedback and motivation. GPS-trajectories are recorded and made available for further analysis. While most dedicated tracking devices and smart watches with GPS-functionality

store their information locally, fitness-tracking apps usually upload data to the app-provider for storage and further analysis. Widely spread fitness-tracking apps are Strava⁴⁴ (popular with sports-cyclists), Runkeeper⁴⁵ (popular with runners) as well as Fitbit or Google Fit.

Most fitness-tracking apps do not allow access to recorded trajectories other than to the user itself. Users are however able to download their own recorded data or give consent for it to be downloaded. Fitness-tracking apps can therefore be used as recorders of trajectories for small scale studies, e.g. on a specific route where data is collected by city staff or by volunteers willing to share their data.

One provider, Strava, makes aggregated data available for research and transport planning through the service Strava Metro. Previously, this data was provided through paid licenses, but Strava changed its policy and is currently providing data to municipalities who apply for it for free.

Collected data

Fitness-data apps where individual trajectories can be downloaded with the consent of the user usually provide data in an unprocessed format which is rich on information but demands additional processing before it can be used. Collecting and processing a larger number of individual trajectories can therefore be resource-intensive.

Strava's aggregated data on a city-level is delivered in the form of aggregated trip numbers on a road-segment level. Each road segment is attributed with aggregated user information such as age and gender, as well as trip direction and average travel speed. Strava allows the users to classify trips as leisure or commute and the aggregated data can be filtered using these two categories. Unclassified trips are automatically assigned either a leisure or commute tag based on extrapolation of trip patterns tagged by the user, trip distance, time of day and the spatial relation between a trip's origin and destination.

Being a dedicated fitness app, the majority of recorded tracks are classified as leisure trips and the distribution of these trips can differ from every-day trips. The number of trips classified as commuting is however increasing, in some cities the number of logged commutes now exceeds logged recreational trips. This is partly due to commuting trips being of more frequent nature than recreational trips. Picture 5.20 illustrates the different patterns of Strava users' leisure and commuting trips for the city of Banja Luka in Bosnia Herzegovina.

⁴⁴ <https://www.strava.com/>

⁴⁵ <https://runkeeper.com>

Picture 5.20: Heat-maps representing the volume of Strava-recorded bicycle-rides in the city of Banja Luka (Bosnia Herzegovina) during 2021. In total, 15 000 tracks were recorded. The left picture is based on all trips, the middle picture on trips labelled as leisure and the right picture on trips labelled as commuting. Source: City of Banja Luka/Strava

Representativeness and reliability of results

Aggregated data from fitness-apps is inherently biased. Firstly, only people interested in recording their physical activities and training are likely to use them. Secondly, users predominantly record their training rides or runs rather than their everyday use of bicycles or inner-city walks and the chosen routes for these two types of bicycle use can differ significantly. In their literature review on the use of Strava Metro data⁴⁶, Lee and Sener conclude that research should not entirely depend on this data source, but that its potential uses increase if it is validated and combined with other data-sources.

Despite its shortcomings, aggregated data from Strava Metro can still have its merits. It provides a clear picture on what routes often are used for sports and leisure-rides. This can be of interest in itself, e.g. to improve the safety of these routes or to develop touristic products.

Further, Strava Metro heat-maps on commute-trips can provide some first, rough insight about travel patterns and what road sections are most frequently used if other information is lacking.

Conclusions

Fitness apps that allow the user to download data can provide a simple and cheap solution if small numbers of trajectories need to be collected for a specific question. For example, city-staff can use them to test travel or waiting times along a route of interest or to evaluate the impact of temporary intervention on travel time. Small numbers of cyclists could also be recruited to track specific routes and to share their data. Data from fitness apps can also be used to test and

⁴⁶ Kyhhyun Lee, Ipek Nese Sener, 2020: Strava Metro data for bicycle monitoring: a literature review. *Transport Reviews*, *Transport Reviews*, 41:1, 27-47

experiment with trajectory data at low cost to gain experience, e.g. before engaging in larger projects collecting user-data with dedicated apps.

Aggregated data from Strava Metro can provide some first insight into the distribution of bicycle traffic in a city and its surrounding, especially if there is a sufficient number of commuting trips recorded. It can be used to get an impression of which street segments or routes are heavily used and the time-distribution of bicycle traffic. Examples of use are studies to identify suitable locations for bicycle volume counting that are representative of volumes throughout the city, as tested in Ottawa, Canada⁴⁷.

However, the information should be used with care and in combination with other data sources, considering its bias and limitations.

Previously, Strava licensed its data to municipalities, at relatively high cost. However, the company has changed its business model and currently (early 2022), municipalities can request access to Strava Metro data from their territory at no cost. This provides an opportunity to test app-based data, to learn about the use of aggregated trajectory-data and to experiment at little risk.

6.7 MULTI-APP BASED LOCATION SERVICES

Introduction

Almost every mobile phone contains applications that offer so called *Location Based Services* (LBS) today. LBS-apps detect the geographical location of the phone and then provide services based on the location information.

Examples of LBS-apps are navigation apps (e.g. *Google Maps*), social media platforms (e.g. *Snapchat*, *Facebook*, *WhatsApp*), games where the phone's position is used (e.g. *Pokemon Go*), fitness apps, weather apps, public transport apps and many more.

LBS-apps collect real-time information on the phones position and movement based on several techniques such as⁴⁸:

- GPS
- triangulation of cell-towers
- WiFi- and Bluetooth networks (through the physical IP address of that network)
- Embedded sensors in the phone (accelerometers)

The app sends the phones position to the service provider which returns specific information based on the location, e.g. where the nearest restaurant can be found, navigational services or tags an uploaded photo with the location. Some LBS-apps send location data only when they are actively used, but many register and send position data in the background even when they are not actively used (if location services are on).

⁴⁷ Brum-Bastos, Vanessa, Colin J. Ferster, Trisalyn Nelson, and Meghan Winters. 2019. "Where to Put Bike Counters? Stratifying Bicycling Patterns in the City Using Crowdsourced Data." *Findings*, November. <https://doi.org/10.32866/10828>.

⁴⁸ <https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/5386-location-based-services.html>

The highest precision can be achieved by using GPS-data but this is battery-draining and limited indoors. Therefore, LBS-apps use several techniques to determine the phones position with as little energy-use as possible. The level of location precision varies depending on the technique used at each instant, from 5-50 metres.

Since LBS-apps are widely used, they allow for the collection of location information from a large part of the population. Providers of LBS-apps use this information both to provide location specific information to the users but also to gather statistical information about specific locations. Examples are navigation apps that offer real-time estimations of congestion and travel time based on information gathered from the phones of drivers or estimations about how crowded a specific shop or restaurant is at a given time – see picture 5.21.

Picture 5.21: Google-maps is probably one of the most used LBS-apps today. By gathering location-data from users' phones, it can collect and present information on how busy a certain shop is at a given time. The example above shows how busy the Systembolaget-shop in central Uppsala is at a given time. Source: GoogleMaps

Position and trajectory-data from LBS-apps is theoretically a very rich data-source for estimating travel patterns or the amount of people at a certain location, especially if data from many LBS-apps can be aggregated.

This service is provided by companies that aggregate large numbers of LBS-datasets from various sources and process this data with AI-algorithms for data fusion and mode recognition. Examples are *Cuebic* and *Street Light Data*.

Street Light Data provides services offering data on bicycle and pedestrian traffic based on crowdsourced information from LBS-apps. Currently, these services are only available in the USA and Canada.

Collected data

Based on a large number of collected positions and trajectories that are collected through LBS-apps combined, calibration data from physical sensors and advanced data-processing, multi-app based location services can extract a range of traffic related data. The used traffic mode is estimated based on parameters such as speed and location. Information that can be extracted for each mode is:

- trip-volumes between and within zones (origin-destination data)
- estimated traffic flows on routes or street segments
- heat-maps
- modal split data
- statistics on trip-attributes (travel distance, speed) as well as

- demographic information such as income or age (based on other data collected by the apps providing position data)⁴⁹.

Picture 5.22: Example of presentation of data on bicycle traffic extrapolated from LBS-app data by the service Street Light Data. Note that the number of samples is not presented. Source: Streetlight Data

Privacy

The collection of LBS-data to some extent authorised by the user by accepting the terms of use of specific apps, but providing position-data is often no active choice (opt-in). Many users are probably not aware of that their position-data is collected and stored and could be used without their knowledge.

LBS-position data can, at least when not heavily aggregated, be used to track and store information of individuals. Their use therefore raises privacy concerns and is partly regulated by law. The *General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR)* of the European Union is stricter than U.S. privacy law⁵⁰. This is probably a key reason why traffic-data from multi-app based location services currently is **not available in Europe**.

Representativeness and reliability of results

Due to the large number of users, their relatively high spatial precision and calibration against other data, e.g. permanent counters, data from multi-app based location services can be considered as both representative and reliable. Some bias in the sample can be expected, since certain groups are likely to use LBS-apps more frequently than others. However, due to the growing ubiquity of LBS-apps, this bias is expected to diminish over time.

⁴⁹ <https://www.streetlightdata.com/bike-pedestrian-traffic-analytics/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.streetlightdata.com/what-transportation-data-analytics/>

Conclusions

Theoretically, multi-app-based location services (MABLS) could provide representative and detailed information on pedestrian and cycling traffic within the whole area of a city. The spatial resolution does not allow for analysis on a detailed infrastructure level (e.g. what side of a road has been used), but can nevertheless provide information down to a street-segment level.

However, there are also clear drawbacks. Position-data is collected from many sources by the MABLS-provider. This implies that user of the data has little to no possibility to verify the origin of the information or its reliability. Data sources might even vary depending on the popularity of certain apps or on the business-arrangements between the MABLS-provider and the owners of LBS-data. The collected data further needs to undergo advanced processing and analysis before it can be used. This complexity – of both obtaining and processing large quantities of position data – implies that only a few, specialised companies can be expected to offer such services. This puts the users at risk of becoming dependent on one of a few data-providers.

Finally, advanced multi-app based location services such as *Street View* are currently **not offering their services in Europe**, probably due to difficulties to adhere to European privacy legislation or the willingness of LBS-app owners to provide user-information to third parties.

Since MABLS-data could be an interesting source of information for traffic planning should it becomes available in Sweden in the future, it is presented nevertheless. Even in such a case, it should primarily be considered as a complementary source of information to avoid creating dependencies on a single provider.

6.8 CELL-TOWER MOBILE PHONE POSITIONING

Introduction

Mobile phone signals have limited range and to be able to call or send data, they need to connect to a network of cell-towers/base stations. When communicating with a base station, the phones number/id, time and which tower it connected to is recorded for operation and billing reference. This allows to associate a specific phone to the location of that station. If the phone moves and the connection to the base station gets weaker, it will connect to another station with a stronger signal. Based on the recorded data, a trajectory of the movement of the phone can thus be recorded.

Depending on the conditions of the site, 3G/4G base stations can cover a radius from a few to dozens of kilometres. However, base stations have a limited capacity how many phones/calls they can handle at once. In areas with high levels of use, the density of base stations therefore needs to be higher. In suburban areas masts can be 2-3 km apart, in dense urban areas the distance between base-stations can be a little as a few hundred metres.

The higher the density of base-stations, the higher the precision of recorded trajectories can become. Typically, the spatial precision of cell-tower positioning data is in the range of 200 to 1 000 metres⁵¹.

Collected data

For each base station, the number of connected phones at any time can be extracted which can be used to observe crowding in a certain area in real time or to register activity-levels/density of people across the city and how it changes over time.

Picture 5.23: Distribution of base station activities in Copenhagen, an indicator for population density at the time of recording. Source: Telia

For every phone connected to the system, trajectories can be constructed by using the location of base-stations and the time of connection. In aggregated form, this allows for origin-destination studies (from where to where people move and when), estimations of travel speed and volumes. By using data from base stations along major roads, the intensity of use can be estimated along road segments for any given time.

The distribution of travel mode can however not be determined directly, nor can trips be separated by mode. It might in some cases be possible to sort trajectories by traffic mode through advanced data processing, by using proxies such as speed or specific locations, e.g. motorways or rail tracks.

However, in mixed traffic in urban areas speed differences between modes are small and the distance between infrastructure for different modes short. This makes it very difficult to distinguish between travel modes. Further, very short

⁵¹ Kyuhyun Lee, Ipek N. Sener, 2020. Emerging data for pedestrian and bicycle monitoring: Sources and applications. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives* 4 (2020)

trips (up to a few hundred metres) can be difficult to detect, both because the phone might not change base station and because the spatial resolution is low.

Privacy

Since the method theoretically allows to produce trajectories of individuals over a long time, it raises considerable privacy concern. For this reason, mobile phone operators are very restrictive concerning access to data to third parties. To avoid privacy issues, data needs to be highly aggregated.

Representativeness and reliability of results

Given the very high levels of mobile phone ownership and use in Sweden, the collected data can be considered highly representative as long as network-data from one or several major mobile-phone operators is used.

Conclusions

Cell-tower mobile phone positioning data cannot on its own provide information on pedestrian or bicycle flows. The key reason is that it is very difficult to detect traffic modes in urban areas and that the method is poor at recording short trips.

On a larger, regional level however, the method can provide very detailed and precise information on regional mobility patterns, for example the numbers of incoming and outgoing commuters, where they come from, where they go to and when. It can therefore provide valuable insight for regional travel planning.

A further application is crowd control, where the number of people in a certain area can be measured in real time or an alarm can be triggered if a certain threshold of people is reached.

The method demands access to data owned by telecom-companies and capabilities to process very large volumes of data. This significantly reduces the number of possible providers of cell-tower based information. In Sweden, only the telecom-provider *Telia* is currently known to offer this kind of services⁵². This puts the users at risk of becoming dependent on a single provider of information.

6.9 SUMMARY OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR TRAFFIC FLOW MEASUREMENT

As illustrated in this chapter, a multitude of different methods to measure pedestrian- and cyclist-flows exist, each with different properties. They can all generate data that can provide valuable insights if they are applied appropriately.

However, no method currently exists that on its own can provide all necessary data to fully understand bicycle or pedestrian flows in a city.

The choice of method(s) therefore needs to be based on the questions that should be answered, what reliability, precision and representativeness of data is necessary and the available budget. Table 5.2 summarises key characteristics of different measuring methods.

⁵² <https://business.teliacompany.com/crowd-insights>

	Inductive loops, piezo	Active infrared	Passive infrared	Radar	Camera, direct processing	Camera, post-processing	WiFi	Local app-based tracking	Fitness app-based tracking	Multi-app location service	Cell-tower mobile phone positioning
Gate counts	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	-
Areal counts (measured, not calculated)	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	-	-	X	X
Trajectories	-	-	-	-	X	X	(4)	X	(4)	(4)	(4)
Direction of travel	(14)	-	-	X	X	X	(14)	X	X	X	X
Speed	(14)	-	-	X	X	X	-	X	X	-	X
Typical resolutions, metres	-	-	-	-	0,1	0,1	50	5	5	25	200-1000
Typical radius covered, metres	-	-	-	-	20	20	100	5km	5km	5km	100 km
Real time data	X	X	X	X	X	X	(1)	-	-	-	(1)
Possible temporal resolution (8)	1s	1s	1s	1s	1s	1s	(9)	30d (12)	30d	1d	(9)
Bicycles measured	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Pedestrians measured	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X
Motor vehicles measured	(2)	-	-	(2)	X	X	(2)	-	-	X	X
Mode differentiation	-	-	-	X	X	X	-	-	-	(3)	(3)
Full municipal control over equipment and data	X	X	X	X	(6)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Own accesses to raw-data	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	(13)	-	-	-
Dependency on (single) provider, purchased data	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	X
Potential privacy concerns	-	-	-	-	-	X	(10)	X	-	-	(11)
Representative data	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X
Suitable for temporary measurements	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	X	X
Suitable for continuous/long time measurements	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	(5)	X	X	X
Investment & installation cost (7)	***	*	*	**	***	**	***	**	-	-	-
Operating cost/fees (7)	*	*	*	*	**	***	**	***	*	***	***

Table 5.2: Characteristics of different measuring systems for pedestrian and cycle-traffic. Notes: 1: for counts, not for trajectories 2: possible, dependent on location 3: can be estimated with advanced data processing, but not with certainty 4: only aggregated 5: possible, but difficult to maintain user-base. 6: Freestanding solutions are possible, but in most cases, data is sent to and processed by the service provider. 7: Observe that the presented cost-indications only are indicative. 8: Possible temporal resolution describes the smallest possible aggregation-unit in time by the system. If every passage can have a time-stamp, 1 second is used. 9: For counts within an antenna location or area – minutes, for trajectories/flow data: hours 10: Privacy concerns if full MAC-address of phones is stored, solved if randomised parts are stored for statistical fingerprinting. 11: Theoretically significant privacy concerns if phone-numbers or MAC-addresses are available; however, not in aggregated form. 12: For counts – 30 days or more. For individual trajectories: seconds. 13: Depending on the chosen supplier/solution. 14: Possible, but not all systems.

General cost-comparisons are difficult since they are highly dependent on what data is requested, and the situation at any given location. Further, system costs can vary significantly within any of the presented system-categories. The rough cost-indications in table 5.2 should therefore only be seen as indicative.

For systems that measure the physical presence of a pedestrian or cyclist directly (with sensor, cameras or WiFi-antennas), the number of measuring spots directly influences costs. The higher the desired spatial resolution/sensor density or the larger the area that should be covered, the higher the cost. An appropriate balance between the size of the area to be covered, a number of measuring spots that allows relevant insight and affordability needs to be found.

For local app-based tracking, the costs consist of the initial cost to licence or develop a suitable app, the cost of marketing efforts to recruit and maintain users as well as ongoing support- or subscription-fees. The cost of recruiting a sufficiently large user base should not be underestimated as it can be a significant part of the total cost.

For systems where users are tracked through their own mobile phones (with apps), costs can be divided in the cost of the actual service – start-up, development or licensing fees and fees for ongoing support and data processing – and the cost of recruiting users that provide data, e.g. through marketing or rewards. For the latter, cost is fundamentally correlated to the number of users. The cost of recruiting and maintaining a sufficiently large user base should not be underestimated and can be a significant part of the total cost.

However, if aggregated trajectories from fitness-apps are sufficient for the question at hand, the fitness-app operator Strava currently provides this data to municipalities for free.

7 What method for what use?

7.1 INTRODUCTION

The starting point of any process to select methods for the acquisition of data on bicycle or pedestrian traffic should always be reflections on the following key questions:

- What do we want to know? (**Not** what data do we need.)
- Why do we want to know it? What improvements can be achieved by this knowledge, in what way will it inform or influence decisions?
- How precise, reliable and representative does the information need to be to allow for well-founded decisions?
- Who is going to use this knowledge and in what format will it be best received?
- How much is this knowledge worth? How valuable are the potential improvements, efficiency gains or the possibility to avoid mistakes that are dependent on the requested information?

Those question are difficult and can in most cases not be answered exhaustively but should nevertheless be discussed before engaging in data acquisition. They can help to create a framework for the process of selecting a suitable method, both in terms of what results are desired as well as what costs are acceptable.

Picture 6.1: It is preferable to define a purpose before engaging in data-collection. Source: Unknown.

Once the key questions above have been answered, the process of selecting a suitable method can start.

It is important to note that none of the identified data-acquisition methods on its own is suitable to provide adequate information for all questions that can be relevant for the planning of bicycle- or pedestrian traffic.

Therefore, the method that is best suited to answer the question at hand needs to be identified. For some questions, it might be necessary to combine data from different measuring methods.

7.2 QUESTIONS AND SUITABLE METHODS

In this section, several questions concerning bicycle and pedestrian traffic that require the acquisition of data are presented. They are partly based on the suggested uses for data presented in Uppsala's tender document for this study.

For each question, suitable data acquisition methods are presented. The choice of methods is primarily based on the analysis in chapter 5, but also alternative, non-technical solutions are presented. In some cases, suppliers are named, but primarily methods are recommended rather than specific suppliers.

How does walking and cycling develop in the city at large?

The levels of walking and cycling on a city-level can be expressed both relatively as *modal split* – the proportion of walking and cycling of all trips – or in absolute terms, expressed in *number of trips* or the *aggregated trip lengths* for each mode.

Especially modal split values are commonly used as indicators for the level of use of different transport modes in a city and to define politically set target values, e.g. when an increase in cycling is desired.

Traditionally, data on trip frequency, trip length, modal choice and information on origin and destinations of trips is collected through *travel surveys*. Travel surveys are usually conducted on a municipal, regional or national level. They provide detailed information but are costly, since many respondents is necessary to achieve representative results. They are therefore only conducted infrequently. Travel surveys also have the drawback that they represent the situation at the time of the survey which might lead to misleading result for transport modes with seasonal variation.

If it is desired to follow **trends in the development of cycling or walking** from year to year or to understand seasonal variations, aggregated data from several counting stations in the city can be used as an indicator. All methods that can provide reliable gate-counts for the desired mode can be used for data-collection.

Ideally, only data from permanent counting stations is used since the results from temporary counts can be influenced by weather conditions during the measuring period. If results from temporary counts are used as well, they need to be calibrated against data from permanent counting stations.

Counting stations should be placed along key routes where a majority of the traffic flow occurs, ideally forming one or several "city-rings" that are passed by all or a majority of trips in the city. The quality of the result is dependent on the choice of measuring locations. For Uppsala, the inner-city ring (*Innerstadssnittet*) that already is used for monitoring motorised traffic could be suitable for bicycle traffic as well, preferably complemented with a smaller "central ring" covering the very city centre.

A baseline-value for a specific year can then be collected as a starting point for comparisons over time. For comparability of results, the location of measuring stations should not be changed. If it is changed, a new baseline measurement is necessary. However, additional measuring stations can be added without compromising comparability.

If the flows of other traffic modes are measured at the same locations as well, also trends in the development of the modal split can be followed. Camera-based

measuring systems facilitate this since they can measure flows of several traffic modes simultaneously.

Opt-in measuring methods such as tracking-apps are not suitable for measuring traffic-development over time, since it cannot with certainty be determined whether changes in counts depend on changed traffic flows or changes in the level of uptake and reporting. Methods that passively measure the use and position of phones can however provide valuable additional information on traffic flows at large.

Suitable methods:

All measuring methods that are suitable **for gate-counts** of the desired mode can be used and the setup of one or several “measuring rings”. Ideally, permanent counting stations that measure continuously are used on all entry points. However, cost can be prohibitive in situations with many entry points. In such cases, permanent counting stations should be used at entry points with the highest expected traffic flows, complemented with temporary measurements at other entry points. Data from the permanent measuring stations can be used to calibrate the result from temporary counts.

Methods that can register the direction of travel are preferable to be able to differentiate between incoming and outgoing traffic.

Ideally, all data-collection is automated. For locations with several traffic modes without existing counters, **video-based systems** should be considered since they can provide data on all modes simultaneously.

Cell-tower mobile phone positioning can provide additional information on total traffic movements on a city-scale, but cannot reliably differentiate between modes.

How does walking and cycling develop within a limited area?

To measure the development of cycling or walking within a more limited area of the city, e.g. the inner-city district, a specific neighbourhood or a pedestrian zone, a “ring” of counting stations (gate-counters) surrounding the area can be used. Ideally, movements on all entry- and exit routes are measured to provide an accurate areal-count of bicycles or pedestrians entering or leaving the area. If this is not possible, at least the traffic flows at the main entry points to the area should be measured.

Ideally, permanent counting stations are used on all entry points, but at least one measuring point should have a permanent counter. If temporary counts are used, the data needs to be calibrated against the results of the permanent measuring station to estimate yearly figures.

Suitable methods:

All measuring methods that are suitable **for reliable gate-counts** of the desired mode can be used. Methods that can register the direction of travel are preferable to be able to differentiate between incoming and outgoing traffic.

For locations with several traffic modes, **video-based systems** should be considered since they can provide data on all modes simultaneously. For pedestrian-only areas, also **WiFi-based systems** are a suitable option.

What are the most popular routes and segments for walking and cycling?

A good understanding of the distribution of pedestrian- or bicycle-traffic between different street segments and routes is valuable for several reasons: It can help to prioritize in infrastructure planning as well as maintenance efforts. It can show in what areas of the city cycling is more or less common and highlight important corridors. An analysis of popular and less popular routes can further provide insight into the perceived quality of routes and the preferences of cyclists, e.g. if they take detours to avoid certain sections.

An understanding of where the largest flows of cyclists or pedestrians occur is also helpful to identify suitable locations for gate-measurements.

Typically, the relative distribution of cyclist- or pedestrian-flows is presented in the form of *heat-maps*, indicating the level of use on each street-segment. Large-scale heat-maps typically show the relative distribution of traffic between street segments, not absolute values for traffic flow. However, by calibrating heat-map data against data from permanent counting stations, absolute traffic volumes on different road sections can be roughly estimated for the entire network. This demands that the heat-map data can be considered representative, which is not always the case.

Heat-maps for cycling- or pedestrian flows can be produced in several ways, mainly depending on the size of the area to be studied:

Small areas:

In areas of limited size such as a specific neighbourhood or a pedestrian area, it is feasible to conduct gate-counts on all street-segments or intersections in the study area (permanent or temporary). This provides a reliable heat-map of the traffic movements on a segment level. Such detailed analysis can be suitable ahead of planning local infrastructure changes, to study the impact of street-work on route-choice or to evaluate the impact of local interventions. In pedestrian areas, high-precision heat maps can provide insight for urban development, crowd management and localization studies.

Suitable methods:

Any applicable **gate-counting** method or **camera-based systems** can be used. For pedestrian areas, **WiFi-based systems** are also suitable and can be cost-efficient, especially if already existing WiFi-antennas can be utilised. Even **manual counts** can be suitable for short-term measuring campaigns in small areas.

Larger areas, city-wide:

For larger areas, it is currently not feasible to directly measure traffic flows on each road section on-site – the number of necessary sensors simply becomes too high to be affordable. This could change in the future, if low-cost camera-based systems become widely available or if crowd-source data-collections gains in acceptance (Such as the Telraam-system where camera-based systems are installed in private homes).

Until then, detailed heat-maps on bicycle-flows can be produced by collecting and aggregating large numbers of GPS-trajectories from cyclists who track their routes. The reliability of results is largely dependent on the number of tracks

recorded and how representative the user-base is. This should always be considered when interpreting the results.

Suitable methods:

Appropriate methods are **tracking-apps** specifically designed for local data-collection such as *BikeCitizen* or *GéoVelo*. A sufficient number of tracks need to be recorded to provide relevant results, ideally by a large and representative user-base. Marketing efforts to attract many users during a limited period such as the Dutch "bike-measuring-week", or built-in rewards to motivate long-term use of the app might be necessary to collect a sufficient number of trajectories.

Also the **fitness-app** *Strava* can provide heat-map data that can be useful, but the specific profile of the user base and type of trips recorded must be considered carefully when interpreting results. Since cities currently can access data from *Strava* at no cost, it could be used as a starting point to gain experience in using GPS-trajectory data, despite its obvious bias.

Where are bottlenecks that slow cyclists or pedestrians down, where do pedestrians linger?

In urban traffic, actual travel speed is to a large extent influenced by waiting times at intersections or crossings. Long waiting times can also induce unwanted and potentially unsafe behaviour such as running red lights. It can therefore be of interest to identify locations with long waiting times for further investigation and improvement. Also road sections where the speed of cyclists is significantly reduced can be of interest, since they can be indicative for unsafe traffic conditions or crowding.

Information on the speed-distribution of cycle traffic and where waiting times occur can be gathered by analysis of aggregated GPS-tracks -see picture 6.2. For a city-wide analysis, the number of recorded tracks needs to be high to cover all road segments and to provide a sufficient base for analysis.

To analyse the speed-distribution and waiting times along a specific route – e.g. for a detailed analysis of a route for bicycle commuting – the number of necessary trajectories is significantly lower and 10-100 trajectories can already provide considerable insight.

Representativeness of the user-base is less critical for an analysis of waiting-times or speed than for heat-maps since these factors are less influenced by the type of cyclist or type of trip.

For pedestrian traffic, speed patterns and where people wait or linger can also be of interest - e.g. to improve signalling at crossings or to determine where benches or waste-baskets best should be located.

Suitable methods:

Tracking-apps specifically designed for local data-collection such as *BikeCitizen* or *GéoVelo* are suitable for large-scale collection of cycle-trajectories. The providers of these apps can also provide tools and assistance for processing the collected data.

For smaller-scale measurements along a specific route, also free-to-use **fitness-apps** that allow to export recorded trajectories (e.g., *Strava*, *Runkeeper*) can be utilised for data collection. In this case, a sufficient number of users -or city staff

– need to be recruited and motivated to record trajectories along the route that is studied and to provide them to the municipality for further processing.

For pedestrian areas, **WiFi-based systems** such as *BumbeeLabs* can provide the desired information.

Where and how long do people have to wait at crossings? Example shows Vienna. Grafic: Bike Citizens

Picture 6.2: Distribution of waiting time at junctions for cyclists in Vienna. Red areas indicate places with average waiting times over 45 seconds. Picture: Bike Citizen.

Where should infrastructure be improved?

A direct way to identify locations where improvements in infrastructure are desirable and what the problem is, is asking the users themselves. This can be done by specific surveys using map-based survey tools such as *Maptionnaire* or by systematically analysing incoming complains. Picture 6.3 shows the results of a large survey in which cyclists in Copenhagen were asked to report their experience.

Some municipalities also use specific apps where users can report faults in the cycle-infrastructure. An example is the app *Cykelstaden*⁵³ by the City of Gothenburg that allows users to directly send reports to the municipality, including the location and pictures of the problem-area.

Suitable methods:

User-surveys, utilizing survey-tools that allow to localise and describe problem areas, **reporting-apps**.

⁵³ <https://goteborg.se/wps/portal/start/gator-vagar-och-torg/cykling-och-cykelvagar/cykelpumpar-och-servicestallen>

Picture 6.3: Results from a user-survey in bicycle-infrastructure in Copenhagen. Red dots indicate areas where cyclists reported that they lack a bike-lane, black dots indicate areas where the bike-lane is considered too narrow and blue dots crossings that are considered crowded. Source: City of Copenhagen

What is the impact of interventions, e.g., deviations or new infrastructure?

Permanent or temporary changes in infrastructure, e.g., a new bike-lane or temporary roadworks can influence bicycle- and pedestrian flows as well as route-choice. This effect can be studied either by local traffic counts or by studying changes of trajectories.

The impact of significant long-term changes such as a new bike-lanes or road closures on route-choice and cycling volumes can be studied by following the development of permanent counts as well as heat-maps of cycling-volumes that also can indicate changes in route-preferences.

To understand the impact of more local or short-term interventions, trajectories of affected users before and during the intervention can be used to analyse the impact on travel time as well as on route choice. Ideally, users that are affected by the intervention, e.g. bicycle commuters that pass the location regularly, are recruited to record their trajectories before and during the intervention.

Another option is to collect information of affected users by interviews or questionnaires.

Suitable methods:

Tracking-apps specifically designed for local data-collection such as *BikeCitizen* or *GéoVelo* are suitable for large-scale collection of cycle-trajectories. For smaller-scale measurements also free-to-use **fitness-apps** that allow to export recorded trajectories (e.g. *Strava*, *Runkeeper*) can be utilised for data collection.

For pedestrian areas, **WiFi-based systems** such as *BumbeeLabs* can provide the desired information.

Further, **user-surveys** or **interviews** can be used to collect information from the users directly.

How many people aggregate at a certain location (crowd detection)?

In some situations it is desired to keep track of the number of people within a certain location – e.g. to measure the popularity of specific sights, to avoid crowding, to ensure safety and security or to identify where more public infrastructure such as waste-bins or benches are necessary. This can be the case when evaluating a pedestrian zone, at big public events but also during demonstrations or in any popular area where a lot of people gather.

If the key-question is the number of persons rather than the number of vehicles, both camera-based methods as well as methods that register the presence of active mobile phones are possible options.

Suitable methods:

What method is suitable is mainly dependent on the geographical scale and necessary spatial precision. For **smaller areas** such as smaller squares (20-30 m diameter), **camera-based measuring systems** or a **WiFi-based systems** with a single antenna can be sufficient. Camera-based systems have the advantage that they also can differentiate between modes.

For larger areas and very high numbers of people, **WiFi-based systems** with multiple measuring points or even **cell-tower mobile phone positioning** can provide real-time approximations of the number of people present. The telecom-operator *Telia* is offering services to count the number of people in certain locations in real time and to trigger an alert if a certain threshold is reached through its service *Crowd Alerts*⁵⁴.

Is the infrastructure used as intended? How do users behave? What was the impact of a design change?

Detailed studies of user behaviour can be necessary to understand if a certain junction works as intended or if changes are necessary or what difference a design intervention has made. Examples are studies of the impact of changed signalling, of changes in the right-of-way, speed-reduction measures or of temporary deviations at roadworks. Further, detailed studies on a junction/segment level can provide insight in how and where conflict situations occur, e.g. between cyclists and pedestrians or cyclists and cars.

Manual observation studies can generate a certain insight, but for more long-term and systematic measurements and analysis, camera-based systems that record exact trajectories of passing vehicles, pedestrians and bicycles are recommended.

⁵⁴ <https://www.telia.se/foretag/losningar/produkter-tjanster/crowd-alerts>

Picture 6.4: Trajectories of almost 20 000 cyclists passing through an intersection during the cycling-event Vätternrundan. Blue indicates the route intended by the organisers. The measurement clearly showed that a majority of cyclists chose shortcuts rather than the intended route. Source: Koucky (2021).

Suitable methods:

Camera-based measurement systems with high spatial resolution and the possibility to reliably differentiate between traffic modes and to record trajectories, e.g. the system from *Viscando*. The system should allow detailed, post-measurement analysis of trajectories, e.g. of speed-distribution, waiting times or to automatically detect conflict-situations.

How to provide reference data for traffic models?

All traffic models, whether they model large-scale traffic flows or micro-modelling of a specific intersection, need to be calibrated against reliable reference data from real-life traffic. Reference-data is also necessary as an “anchoring point” to calibrate temporary counts or to extrapolate traffic flows from heat-map data.

Crucial for data used for calibration is its reliability and precision. Therefore, methods that count physical traffic flows rather than estimating it by proxy (such as passing mobile phones) should be chosen. Continuous measurements with high temporal resolution are preferable and the chosen method needs to be able to reliably register the traffic volumes at the measuring location. The latter is especially important if large flows can be expected. Many measuring systems provide reliable counts as long as one cyclist or pedestrian follows the other, but loose precision when larger crowds pass the measuring line at the same time.

Suitable methods:

High-precision **camera-based measurement systems** with high spatial resolution are recommended for baseline-measurements, both for gate-counts as well as for intersections. Camera-based systems are best suited to measure large numbers of individual objects. For gate-counts where no crowding is expected, also other gate-counting systems can be suitable. All measuring-systems used for calibration should themselves be controlled every now and then by manual counts.

How to identify locations with high accident-risk?

Traffic safety is an important concern for municipalities. Systematically identifying locations with high accident-risk and understanding the causes of the accidents are important steps towards improved safety. In Sweden, severe accidents (where hospital care is necessary or the police got involved) are systematically reported to a national information system called *Strada*⁵⁵. Municipalities can access information from Strada upon request. Some municipalities such as Gothenburg have systematically recorded the location and background data of severe accidents involving cyclists or pedestrian in a GIS-database for many years. This allows to identify locations with high accident rates as well as to study if specific infrastructure solutions or situations cause higher risks.

Suitable methods:

GIS-database where severe accidents involving cyclists or pedestrians (or other vulnerable groups such as e-scooters) systematically are recorded. Input-data can be requested from the national traffic-accident information system *Strada*.

Surveys for self-reporting of bicycle- or pedestrian accidents. Surveys allow to gather information on less severe accidents that are not reported to *Strada*. The used survey tools should allow to register the exact location of the accident.

⁵⁵ <https://www.transportstyrelsen.se/sv/vagtrafik/statistik/olycksstatistik/om-strada/>

7.3 SUMMARY

Table 6.1 below summarises what methods are suitable for what questions.

	Inductive loops, piezo	Active infrared	Passive infrared	Radar	Camera, direct processing	Camera, post-processing	WiFi	Local app-based tracking	Fitness app-based tracking	Multi-app location service	Cell-tower mobile phone positioning	Other
Measuring traffic flows on regional level										All modes	All modes	
Measuring traffic flows on street-level	B	B+P	B+P	B/P	B/P	B/P	B+P	B	B	B/P	-	
Choice of direction at crossings	-	-	-	-	X	X	-	X	X	-	-	
Development of cycling-/walking, city-wide	2, B	2	2	2	2	2					All modes	Travel survey
Development of cycling/walking, district/smaller area	2	2	2	2	2	2	P					
Distribution of flow between road segments/heat map, city-wide	-	-	-	-	-	-	B+P	B	B	B+C	All modes	
Origin-destination matrix, block-level	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	X	-	
Origin-destination, city-district-level	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	X	X	
Origin-destination, regional-level	B	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	
Speed distribution, dwelling time, bottlenecks	-	-	-	-	-	-	P	B	-	-	-	
Route-choice studies	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	-	X	-	
Real-time crowd detection	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	-	-	-	X	
Detect areas for improvement												Surveys
Impact of intervention							P	X	X			Surveys
Detailed use studies					X	X						Observations
Collect reference data	B			B/P	B/P	B/P						

Table 6.1: Applications for data about bicycle- or pedestrians and what sensor-systems can provide relevant data.
 B: bicycles, P: pedestrians, B+P: both, non-distinguishable, B/P: both, distinguishable 1: Large number of trajectories needed. 2: Only aggregated from several counters.

8 Storage, processing and combination of data

8.1 INTRODUCTION

To become useful, any collected data needs to be available and potential users need to know where to find it. In many cases, raw measuring data further needs processing before it can be used.

These questions, as well as the potential of combining data from different sources is discussed in this chapter.

8.2 DATA STORAGE AND AVAILABILITY

It is not unusual that measurement-data on bicycle- or pedestrian traffic is stored locally by the person or unit that initiated the collection of data and might have a direct use of it. Whilst the persons working directly with it might have good knowledge about the available data, its properties and how to access it, other units or even staff within the same department might not be aware of its availability.

Knowledge about what data is available, where it can be found and its properties also risks to get lost during organisational changes such as change of staff. In the worst case, data is deleted or lost permanently.

To ensure that collected data becomes and remains available within the entire municipal organisation and remains useful for a long time, e.g. for historical comparisons, a structured approach to storage and documentation of data is necessary. The following aspects are important:

Inventory, catalogue

An accessible inventory or catalogue of available datasets on bicycle- and pedestrian-traffic is essential for its systematic use. The inventory should describe the type of data and basic qualities of each dataset (e.g. temporary/permanent counts, period covered etc.), where it is stored, how it can be accessed and ideally also a responsible contact person.

The inventory of available data should be known and accessible within the organisation, with clearly defined responsibility for keeping it up-to-date. An inventory/catalogue of available data on bicycle and pedestrian traffic should include all permanent or temporary traffic counts, but ideally also other data related to walking or cycling in the municipality such as results of surveys or interview studies or traffic-safety data.

Metadata

To be able to interpret the data properly and to judge its suitability for the question at hand, a user needs a thorough understanding of how it has been acquired, its precision, temporal and spatial resolution and possible bias.

Without a proper understanding of these parameters, the interpretation of data might result in misleading conclusions.

It is therefore **essential** that each dataset is accompanied by a set of **metadata** that provides background information. Metadata should be as detailed as possible and contain the necessary information to properly interpret the data. Metadata should also contain information on the conditions for access to the dataset, whether it is open data that can be made accessible to anyone or if restrictions apply, e.g. because of privacy issues.

Examples of parameters that can be part of metadata are:

- time and location of measurement
- used method
- temporal and spatial resolution
- a description of data-format
- responsible person/unit
- sample-size
- raw-data or processed data; if processed – what dataset is it based on, how was it processed, by whom?
- access privileges – who is allowed to access the dataset.

Datasets without corresponding metadata should never be used.

Automated data-entry

For permanent measuring stations that produce a continuous flow of data, data transfer and entry should ideally be automatized with suitable API:s. Most producers of measuring systems offer their own solutions for data-transfer and storage and in some case also processing. If this is the case, it should be ensured that the municipality also receives raw-data rather than only already processed data.

Distributed vs centralised storage

It is possible to provide wide access to bicycle- and pedestrian data if it is stored locally, e.g. on the computer of the person responsible for the measurement. However, this requires a very accurate and up-to-date inventory and that the data-owner has the capacity to extract data upon request. Local storage of measurement results further increases the risk that data gets lost, e.g. when a computer is replaced or a person changes job. Local storage of data also raises issues concerning data-security and privacy.

It is therefore **recommended** to use a **common platform** where data on bicycle- and pedestrian traffic is stored, e.g. a **central repository or data-lake for bicycle- and pedestrian data**. A data-repository does not necessarily need to be restricted to bicycle- or pedestrian traffic. The data could also be included into a repository for municipal digital data on traffic in general or even in a general data-lake for municipal digital data. Essential is that the data is safely stored, well structured, catalogued and accessible. Using the existing platform *Trafficweb* could be an option if data from the permanent counting stations can be integrated. However, specialised platforms like *Trafficweb* usually only offer limited possibilities to integrate other types of data such as weather data, trajectories, survey data or other location-based data. If a platform like

Trafficweb is used, it need to be ensured that all stored data easily can be exported.

Ideally, the development of a repository for bicycle- and pedestrian-data is synchronised with other efforts within the municipality to provide a framework for digital data.

Internal- or external solutions

A repository for bicycle- and pedestrian data could be developed internally, as a part of Uppsala's ongoing efforts to digitalise municipal data. An in-house solution has the advantage that it can be fully adapted to the needs of the municipality and that the municipality can choose freely what data is stored.

An alternative to creating an in-house solution is using a commercial platform for the collection and presentation of traffic data. Examples are *Trafficweb*⁵⁶, a service that is already used by Uppsala Municipality and *SmartTraffic*⁵⁷. Both are primarily designed for data from motorised traffic, but can also accommodate data from bicycle counters. Another example is *Eco-Visio*⁵⁸ that is specifically designed for data from bicycle- and pedestrian counters.

The advantage of using a commercial platform is that they offer built-in possibilities to analyse and visualise data and to some extent automate data-collection. Some platforms are products of companies that also produce or sell measuring equipment (e.g. *Eco-Visio*) and it is uncertain if the platform is well-prepared to import data from equipment from other manufacturers. This could limit the platform's use or create a dependency on that supplier.

The general drawback of commercial platforms for traffic data is that they limit what kind of data can be included. They are primarily designed to handle data from traffic counters and possibly GPS-tracks. Other categories of data that were not foreseen in the platform, e.g. results from user-satisfaction surveys, cannot easily be included. The built-in tools for data-analysis and visualisation that most platforms offer can greatly facilitate data-analysis. They can however also become limiting since the define what types of analysis are possible.

If a commercial platform is used to collect, store and process bicycle- and pedestrian data, it is therefore **recommended** to create a parallel repository for raw-data to avoid full dependency on a supplier, to ensure ownership and control of raw-data and full freedom to analyse the data at will.

8.3 RAW- AND PROCESSED DATA

Raw-data

Ideally, the original dataset with unprocessed raw-data is stored for each measurement. Data with the highest possible temporal and spatial resolution possible by the used sensor should be stored rather than aggregated data.

⁵⁶ <https://trafficweb.io/>.

⁵⁷ <https://www.hadomatic.ch/smarttraffic/>

⁵⁸ <https://www.eco-counter.com/produits/eco-visio-range/eco-visio-5/>

The availability of the original dataset with raw-data provides flexibility in the choice of aggregation-level and also allows to retroactively control processed data or to provide new, processed datasets.

Processed data

In most cases, raw-data from sensors needs to be processed before further use. It might be necessary to “clean” it from obvious errors, to eliminate privacy issues or to aggregate the results to a desired format.

For some purposes it might for example be suitable to present the temporal distribution of bicycle traffic at a measuring point in five-minute intervals, for other purposes an aggregation to days, weeks or months might be more relevant. Raw GPS-tracks might need to be allocated to their nearest road or bike-lane to provide useful information. Data from temporary counts might need to get calibrated against results from permanent counters.

Processing of bicycle- or pedestrian data might also be needed if should be combined with other datasets, for example counts from motorized traffic, air-quality data or weather data. In that case, the temporal- and spatial resolution might need to be adjusted to the same level for both datasets.

Depending on the nature of the collected data, the level of difficulty to process it into a format that is useful can vary significantly. Data from gate-counters is relatively easy to process and aggregate. On the other hand, processing trajectory-data, e.g. from GPS-measurements, can require significant skill and computing power. It can therefore not be assumed that the persons in need of the desired results have the capability to process the data from measurements themselves. In such cases, data-processing might need to be performed by in-house or external specialists based on the requirements of the users of the data.

Whenever data is processed for further use, a new dataset should be produced, with a corresponding set of metadata.

8.4 MAKING DATA AVAILABLE

Internally

To be useful to municipal planners or strategists, data on bicycle and pedestrian traffic needs to be both readily available and in a format that is easily accessible. What data is available and how it can be accessed should be well documented and regularly communicated.

Preferably, a common platform where data easily can be accessed by all interested departments is used.

Ideally, the internal function of a cycle/pedestrian/traffic-data specialist or -unit is created, with the responsibility to store, organise and process all collected data and to assist municipal staff to find and extract the data they need upon demand. This function could be limited to bicycle- and pedestrian data, extended to all traffic-related data or even include other areas with spatial digital data. This demands in-house capacity for data-processing and extraction and a good understanding of the user’s needs.

Externally, open data

All data should be controlled for potential privacy issues or other potential conflicts of interest before being classified as open data that is made available to third parties or the public. Raw-data with no risk for privacy-issues such a gate-count data from permanent counters can be made accessible to third parties in real-time through open API:s.

For all other data, specific datasets for public or third-party use should be generated if needed, processed in such a way that privacy is guaranteed and in a format that is accessible and easy to understand.

Examples of data that could be made available to the public through web-based maps or dashboards with up-to-data information are daily, monthly or annual averages from permanent counters or results from automated areal counts.

An example is shown in picture 7.1 below, with publicly accessible data from a permanent measuring-station on a street in Leuven, Belgium.

Picture 7.1. Example of publicly available measuring-data: Daily results from an automated, camera-based measuring system on a road in Leuven, Belgium. Source: Telraam⁵⁹

8.5 COMBINING DATA FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES

Many questions concerning walking and cycling cannot be answered with one type of data alone. By combining data from different sources, new insights or more reliable results can be achieved.

Examples

Calibrating results from temporary counts. Results from temporary counts of bicycle- or pedestrian traffic are difficult extrapolate to annual average figures or to compare over time, since variations can be caused both by long-term trends as well as temporary factors such as weather conditions. If data from permanent counting stations nearby is available, short-term effects caused by weather can be detected and the results from temporary counts can be calibrated accordingly.

Extrapolate bicycle flows from aggregated trajectories. By aggregating large numbers of trip-trajectories collected by apps, a heat map of the intensity of bicycle use on different street-segments can be created. However, no information on the actual traffic volumes can be extracted since the recorded tracks only represent a small sample of all bicycle trips. By comparing the number of trajectories at places with results from permanent measuring

⁵⁹ <https://telraam.net/en/location/9000002081/2022-02-04/2022-02-04>

stations, the total bicycle flows on other segments can roughly be extrapolated. Even if this method should only be used with care since the sample is small, it still has the potential to provide a rough estimate of the total volume of bicycle traffic in a city.

Assessing cyclists' infrastructure use. By combining GIS-information attributes of the street-infrastructure and traffic flow-data, the proportion of cycling on different types of infrastructure (e.g. segregated bike lane, mixed road <30 km/h, mixed road >30 km/h etc.) within the city area can be assessed.

Understanding changes in modal split. An increase of cycling does not necessarily imply reduction of local emissions, since the additional cyclists might be former public transport users or the increase might be caused by a general increase in traffic for all modes. To better understand the impact of changes in cycling (or walking) volumes, the data therefore needs to be combined with information on the development of other modes at the same location and within the same timeframe.

Identifying areas or user groups with high or low cycling levels. By comparing bicycle flow data on an area-level with demographic data such as population density, income- or employment levels in specific areas, it can be studied whether specific groups or the inhabitants of specific neighbourhoods are more or less inclined to cycle. This information can be useful for further investigations into the reasons for such differences or targeted measures.

Bicycle Observatory – holistic picture of bicycle traffic. The University of Salzburg led a research project on integrating cycling-relevant data in a Bicycle Observatory⁶⁰, using the city of Salzburg as real world lab for the proof of concept.

Instead of single measurements at specific locations and time periods, a Bicycle Observatory facilitates continuous and integrated measurements of cycling-related parameters. The concept is well established in different observational disciplines, such as astronomy, biology or economy. In a demonstrator application the following data sources were tapped and technically integrated: spatial data on the physical environment (infrastructure, land use, weather), movement data, demographic data, crash reports, mobility surveys as well as qualitative data from surveys and feedback apps.

The project showed that the integration of different data sources to provide a more holistic picture of cycle traffic is feasible and promising and that conceptual and technical challenges can be solved. However, it also revealed considerable challenges in terms of data availability, accessibility and quality that need to be overcome before a fully functional Bicycle Observatory can be implemented.

Conclusions

Combining data from different sources is not without challenges. It is not always possible to find a common denominator, even if geographical location often can be used as a common base. Further, the spatial or temporal resolution of the two datasets might differ considerably, as well as sensing/update frequency, data

⁶⁰ <https://bicycle-observatory.zgis.at/en/bicycle-observatory-2/>

model or data formats. Datasets need in most cases considerable processing to adjust for differences in temporal or spatial resolution before they can be combined in a meaningful way.

Nevertheless, the combination of different data sources can open opportunities to create a better understanding and insights that would not be possible otherwise.

9 Conclusions and recommendations for Uppsala

9.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, key conclusions and recommendations for Uppsala are presented. A short summary of recommendations is presented in chapter 10.

Uppsala is by all metrics a successful cycling city. In 2015 it had a modal share of cycling of over 36% in the city-area and 33% within the municipality as a whole⁶¹ which is amongst the highest in Sweden and also ranks it amongst the best cycling cities internationally. The municipality has several times been ranked as the best cycling-city in Sweden by *Cykelfrämjandet*, the largest Swedish association for cyclists.

Clearly, Uppsala municipality does many things right when it comes to cycling and cycle planning. This should be kept in mind when reading the following conclusions and discussions. Better and more data can support planning and decision making and allow for more efficient measures. But it is by no means a guarantee and not even a precondition for successful cycle planning.

With this in mind, this study nevertheless shows that **Uppsala has room for improvement** when it comes to collecting, organising and using data about bicycle- and, even more pronounced, pedestrian traffic. Most of these **challenges are organisational rather than technical and should be addressed ahead of investing in new data acquisition methods.**

9.2 UPPSALA'S CURRENT SITUATION

Bicycle traffic data

The traffic administration of Uppsala already collects and owns a considerable amount of data on cycle-traffic. However, data-collection and management seems to be organised in an ad-hoc manner rather than strategically to answer specific questions or to provide information that directly can be used in planning.

The existing, permanent counting stations can provide relevant baseline information but their number and location limit the strategic use of this data, e.g. to directly compare bicycle flows into the centre to motorised traffic or to reliably determine the volumes of in- and outgoing bicycle traffic and its development over time. It is unclear how the results of temporary counts is used to complement the information from the permanent counter network.

⁶¹ Based on the travel survey from 2015. Source: Uppsala kommun, cykelåret 2020.

Further, the existing data is not yet readily accessible and put to use throughout the municipal organisation.

The city-organisation is interested and open to become more data-driven and some internal resources are in place. Access to more and better data on the development of cycle traffic is desired and considered valuable in itself.

However, it seems less developed **why** data should be collected and how it should be put to practical use. Internal mechanisms and routines to systematically put bicycle-data to use in planning processes seem largely missing.

An understanding of how existing and additional bicycle data can add value to planning or strategic development of measures exists on an individual level, but seems not yet to be institutionalised within the municipal organisation. Creating a more widely spread understanding of the value data can is therefore a key challenge on the way towards a more data-driven organisation.

Pedestrian traffic data

The collection and use of data on pedestrian traffic seems largely underdeveloped. Compared to data on bicycle-traffic or other travel modes, very little information seems to be available or used concerning pedestrian traffic. Some data from the pedestrian zone exists due to the measurements from *Citysamverkan* but seem not to be used systematically by the municipality. Uppsala has significant opportunities to learn more about pedestrian traffic in the city.

Recommendations

Uppsala is recommended to continue its ongoing process of capacity building and to **consider developing an internal strategy and processes for both collecting and using data on bicycle and pedestrian traffic**. This should ideally be done ahead of investing into new data acquisition methods.

Specifically, the municipality is recommended to:

A: Define what information is relevant and why.

Start an internal process to develop a set of questions that, if successfully answered, can improve the planning and deployment of bicycle or pedestrian measures. This process should result in a list of questions that define:

- What does the municipality need to know about bicycle or pedestrian traffic? What **information** is needed (not data)?
- Why is this information needed? What gets better if it is known?
- How can it be put to use?
- Who is going to use it?

Ideally, not only traffic planners but also staff from other units is involved in the process, e.g. from road maintenance, public health, physical planning or strategic planning. Also external stakeholders could be involved, e.g. user associations, business associations or research organisations. However, the needs of the municipality and how additional information can improve the municipal processes should remain in focus.

This process could be organised in the format of one or several internal workshops. The results from workshop 1 within this project (see appendix 3) as

well as a discussion how decisions concerning pedestrian- and bicycle-traffic are taken today could be used as a starting point.

B: Define the (incremental) value of information

In a second step, the **value** that additional information can provide and the necessary **precision and resolution** of this information should be discussed:

- What is the value of the suggested information on walking or cycling? What gets better if this information is available and used? Try to express this value in monetary terms if possible, but at least qualitatively.
- What are the minimal requirements to make the information useful?
- What additional value does higher precision/resolution add? What is gained

The discussion on the value of information and the necessary precision is important and should not be neglected. It is a precondition for an informed cost-benefit analysis that should precede any investment in data acquisition.

First when these steps are concluded, the discussion should move further to what **data** is needed to provide the desired information and what methods are most suitable to collect it.

C: Generate a structured overview of existing data.

As a first step to create a data repository for data on bicycle- and pedestrian traffic, a systematic overview/catalogue of existing datasets should be generated. It should contain information on all existing datasets from bicycle- or pedestrian counts, also from external sources such as *VTI, Trafikverket* or the pedestrian counts from *Citysamverkan*. Other types of bicycle- or pedestrian related data should also be included, such as results of qualitative studies, surveys, tracking-studies or similar.

The catalogue should contain information on the location and time of measurement, the used method, sample size (if applicable) and, most importantly, where the data can be found. A certain overview of counting locations including results already seems to exist as picture 4.1 illustrates, a catalogue could build further on this existing work.

D: Identify information gaps and gaps in availability

The existing data should be compared to the need of information as defined in the previous step to identify:

- Where existing information can be put to use, which of the defined questions can be fully or partially answered.
- For what questions or locations relevant information currently is lacking or is insufficient.
- If this existing information currently is used by the relevant stakeholders.
- If not – investigate why and how this can be remedied.

E: Choose suitable data and data-acquisitions methods

Once it has become clear what information is lacking or would provide additional value, possible sources for necessary data should be identified, compared and finally chosen. An open mind should be kept when investigating

potential data sources – in many cases the desired information can be acquired in several ways, both with physical measurements as well as through user-involvement.

9.3 DATA MANAGEMENT, PROCESSING AND INTEGRATION

Data management and storage

Structured management and storage of data is essential to make it accessible and to allow for long-term comparisons. Ideally, a shared repository for bicycle- and pedestrian data is provided, where data from different sources can be stored and accessed. This might be possible in the existing *Trafficweb*-application the municipality already uses, but most probably this solution is too limited. It might therefore require a specific database-structure or could be integrated in a broader structure for storage of municipal digital data.

Essential is that the data is followed by a systematic, searchable inventory/catalogue and that detailed metadata is associated with each dataset. An inventory is even more essential if data is not (yet) stored in a shared repository but locally. In this case it also needs to contain detailed information about how the data can be accessed or whom to contact. The recommended inventory of all existing data on cycling- and pedestrian travel can be a starting point. A systematic inventory will also greatly facilitate migration of locally stored data to a central repository once this is established.

Regularly updated data such as data from continuous measuring stations should preferably be imported automatically through suitable API:s.

To avoid that potentially sensitive data comes adrift, it is further essential that the chosen IT-structure allows for reliable access-control – either on the level of datasets or through different levels of access on a container-basis.

Data processing

If possible, a set of unprocessed raw-data from measurements should be stored in all cases. Having access to unprocessed raw-data allows for retroactive analysis, e.g. to create datasets with different aggregation-levels as needed.

However, raw-data is in many case of little use without further processing. Before further use, data needs to be controlled for obvious errors and if necessary calibrated against reference values. More complex datasets such as areal counts consisting of multiple sets of gate-counts or large numbers of GPS-trajectories might need considerable processing before their information-content can come to use.

For each dataset, it also needs to be assessed whether it can contain sensitive information, for example causing privacy issues, and it needs to be decided who can be granted access to it.

Raw-data should not be compromised, processed data should be stored in separate datasets and information on the processing steps needs to be stored in the datasets metadata.

Ideally, raw-data is processed and presented in such a way that the end user of the information, e.g. a traffic planner, easily can access, understand and use it.

This demands a dialogue between the person(s) responsible for data processing and the user of data in which it is clarified what information can be extracted as well as what format, level of aggregation etc. is required by the user and how the data best is presented.

Processing of complex and rich measuring data, e.g. GPS-trajectories, might demand considerable skill and computing power. It cannot be assumed that the users of measurement results can conduct data-processing by themselves. Ideally, that service is provided by staff with the necessary expertise, on demand of the users.

Data integration

Integrating and combining data from different sources can provide valuable new insights and new uses for the collected data. Trivial examples are the combination of weather-data with traffic-count data or combining counter-data from different traffic modes. More complex examples of data integration are if traffic-data is combined with demographic information or data on air-quality.

Combining data from different sources and even categories can demand significant processing to allow for a common denominator that allows to connect the two datasets. Data integration therefore demands considerable understanding of the underlying structure and qualities of the used datasets and skills to process them in a way that allows for useful combination.

Recommendations

F: Create an internally accessible catalogue on available data

A digital, searchable catalogue over available data on cycle- and pedestrian traffic should be created and made accessible within the municipality.

If an equivalent catalogue for other traffic data already exists, it could alternatively be expanded to include information on bicycle- and pedestrian traffic. If not, the proposed catalogue could in the future be expanded to also include information about datasets on motorised traffic. The catalogue needs to be accessible for the whole administration and prepared for new entries.

Who should be responsible for the catalogue and where it should be located needs to be decided, as well as what information it should contain, whether it should be presented in list, map or combined form.

The catalogue should at least contain information on the traffic modes, type of data, time and location of measurement, access level (internal, public, restricted), where it can be found and a responsible contact person. The results from recommendation B can be used as a starting point.

G: Create a common standard and routines for metadata

A comprehensive set of metadata is essential for the proper use and interpretation of all data. It is therefore strongly recommended to develop a standardised format and routines to ensure that metadata always is properly associated to its corresponding dataset. Quality-requirements on metadata and the connection to its dataset should be developed in collaboration with Uppsala's IT-unit.

H: Create a common repository for storing bicycle- and pedestrian data

A common repository for bicycle- and pedestrian data should be created – either as a stand-alone database, as part of a larger repository for traffic-related data or as a part of a municipal data-lake. What solution and form that is most suitable needs to be determined in dialogue with the municipalities' experts on data-management and IT. Important is that the data is readily accessible and stored safely.

Once the repository is established, API:s for automated import of data from permanent counter or for export of open data can be integrated.

I: Create a data-expert service

While simple traffic-count data certainly is possible to process by many, handling and processing large amounts of complex data is outside the expertise of traffic experts or planners, especially if trajectory data is used.

It is therefore recommended that the municipality considers establishing the position of one or several **data-experts with the necessary skills** to manage and process large quantities of digital data. This does not need to be limited to pedestrian-, cycle- or even traffic data. For a municipality of the size of Uppsala, that expertise should ideally at least partially be available in-house.

Their task should be to structure and process available data and to provide processed datasets in a suitable and accessible format, according to the user's needs. A further task could be to integrate different datasets to extract new information. These services could be provided on demand from internal or external users.

The proposed function or unit demands significant skill in organising, understanding, handling and processing large datasets in general and traffic- and geographical data in particular. It further demands an ability to understand the users' needs and to communicate the possibilities and limitations implicit in the available data.

It is not likely that the creation of such a qualified, internal function can be justified for bicycle- and pedestrian data alone. Instead, the municipality should consider extend the scope of a big-data specialist or -unit to also serve other areas such as traffic-data, spatial data in general or demographic data. If demand is limited, the task could also be outsourced to external experts.

Uppsala municipality already has considerable internal know-how and capacity for handling geographical information in GIS. This know-how can overlap with the here described demands. Therefore, the possibility for synergies and using existing organisational structures and competencies should be explored.

It is in any case recommended to provide expert support for handling and processing data to a format that is useful and accessible to the users of information.

9.4 MEASURING TECHNOLOGY

The original intention with this project was to identify and recommend suitable solutions to provide Uppsala with detailed data on pedestrian and bicycle-flows. However, during the course of the project, it showed that Uppsala's request

cannot be met by a single data-source alone and that some of the key issues to resolve are organisational rather than technical.

The study nevertheless shows that both existing and new digital technologies can provide valuable additional information if used and combined properly.

The ultimate data-source

A single data-source or sensor-technology that can provide data on the movement of cyclists and pedestrians with high spatial and temporal resolution in real time, is cheap, provides full control over data, high levels of representativity and no privacy issues **does not yet exist** – and probably never will.

For bicycle and pedestrian traffic, it will in a foreseeable future therefore still be necessary to rely on data from physical measuring stations, preferably combined with complementary data from other sources.

Multi-app based location services

Multi-app based location services that collect location data from different apps from a large numbers of mobile phones come closest to the requirements that Uppsala presented in its procurement documents, at least theoretically.

They have relatively good spatial and temporal precision and a very wide sample base. However, they cannot provide real-time data and offer very little transparency concerning the data sources and how data has been processed. The user has little to no control over the underlying data and is fully dependent on the service provider. Traffic modes are assigned to trajectories retroactively by algorithms using parameters like travel speed, which might cause uncertain results in urban traffic.

Most importantly, multi-app based location services are currently not available in Europe, probably because of the relatively strict European legislation on protection of private data. For this reason alone, that method is currently not applicable in Uppsala. But even if it were, it could put the municipality in a position of dependency and other methods would still be needed to complement and verify the results.

Gate-counts are still necessary – the more the better

Permanent gate-counters with automated transmission of data are and will remain an essential tool to measure bicycle and pedestrian traffic. They have the advantage of measuring actual passages of people or bicycles rather than proxies such as mobile phones and can provide data in real time and without privacy concerns.

The information about traffic flows that can be extracted from gate-counts greatly depends on the density and distribution of the counters in the city. A strategically placed, dense network of permanent counters with real-time data transmission could provide a good overview of traffic flows in the city. Such a network can be built up and expanded gradually by stepwise adding gate-counters at more locations – se picture 9.1.

Picture 9.1. Areal counts measure the in- and outflow into a specific area, e.g. an inner city ring by counting passages at entry- and exit gates (marked in yellow). An initial area that is observed (A) can be segmented with additional counters, either by a smaller inner ring (B) or by introducing new “measuring lines” (mätsnitt, C). In that way, more detailed information about traffic movements within the area can gradually be obtained.

The cost of traffic-counting technology and data-transmission can be expected to gradually fall, using small units that are easy to install and might even manage without external power supply. Especially camera-based systems are promising (see next section) and the example of the Belgian *Telraam*-system that uses low-cost sensors and crowdsourcing of measuring-sites shows that a high number of permanent measuring stations is not necessarily unachievable.

Cameras offer additional value

Camera-based measuring systems can offer significant additional value compared to more traditional sensors such as inductive loops or even radar. They can measure traffic flows of different traffic modes simultaneously, can detect travel direction and can produce more reliable results in crowded situation. Placed strategically, a single camera-based system can measure flows across different arms of an intersection, either providing additional information or cutting costs compared to traditional methods.

Camera-based measuring systems can further provide additional information such as speed-data or trajectories for detailed studies of travel behaviour. If pedestrian traffic should be measured in a mixed-traffic environment, camera-based systems are basically the only option.

Compared to methods that use sensors in the road surface, camera-based systems can be cheaper to install and are more flexible since they easily can be moved or change angle. Further, camera-based systems can be expected to get both better and cheaper over time, both because computing-power and high-resolution cameras steadily decreases in cost and advances in AI-based picture-recognition software.

App-based data has limits, but adds valuable information

Trajectory-data collected with apps can provide detailed insights into the distribution of bicycle trips between different street-segments and information on speed distribution and waiting times. App-based trajectory data can therefore be a rewarding complement to counter-data and help to identify important corridors or routes as well as bottlenecks that cause delays.

Challenges are the representativeness of results since the sample might be biased and the usually relatively small number of trajectories compared to the total volumes of bicycle traffic. When dedicated apps for data collection are used, considerable efforts need therefore to be made to recruit a large number of participants and to keep them motivated to use the tracking-app. This can increase the cost of data-collection with apps significantly.

Privacy can be an issue and the collection and use of trajectory demands consent of the user and high levels of aggregation. Processing large numbers of GPS-trajectories is no trivial task and demands special skills not necessarily available within the municipality. However, the providers of specialised tracking-apps usually can offer such services.

Data from dedicated fitness-apps such as Strava cannot be expected to be representative. It can nevertheless provide some insight into what routes are heavily used and further offers an opportunity to test the use of trajectory-based data.

Wi-Fi based systems

Systems that measure the presence of mobile phones through WiFi-antennas have the drawback that they cannot distinguish what traffic mode is used. However, in areas where only pedestrians can be expected or if the travel-mode is of little interest, the method can be a viable alternative. A strength of the method is that it can produce estimates of the number of people within a certain, smaller area like a square or a building in real time. It is therefore well suited for crowd control at specific, smaller sites or events.

Cell-tower mobile phone positioning

Information extracted from data from mobile-phone operators can provide very valuable insight into regional transportation patterns. However, travel modes cannot be distinguished and the spatial precision is too low to extract useful information on bicycle or pedestrian trips.

However, cell-tower data can be very suitable if the number of people within a larger area needs to be estimated, for example within the city centre or during a larger event. It is therefore well suited for crowd control within larger areas.

Recommendations

J: Consider creating one or several inner-city rings of counters

The current distribution of bicycle counters in Uppsala seems not to allow to reliably follow bicycle traffic movements in and out of the inner city, nor to compare the modal share of different modes in real time. It is therefore recommended to create one, or several “city-rings” for measuring bicycle traffic. This would allow for areal counts and to better understand the in- and outflow of

cyclists. Ideally, one “measuring ring” could duplicate the measuring-ring for motorized traffic (innerstadssnittet) to allow for direct comparisons.

In the longer run, additional permanent counters could be added, either as a new measuring ring or to segment the zone in smaller sections, providing additional detail to the information, as illustrated in picture 9.1.

If possible, the existing, permanent counters should be used as a part of suitable measuring-zones, complemented by additional permanent counters. Temporary counts can be used as a way to get started, as long as the data can be calibrated against at least one permanent measuring station.

K: Choose camera-based systems when installing new counters

Camera-based systems offer many added benefits compared to more traditional measuring systems and are therefore recommended if a new measuring-station should be installed. Camera-based systems are also recommended for temporary measurements if a detailed understanding of traffic patterns is desired, e.g. route-choices at a crossing or where conflict-situations occur.

L: Experiment with Strava-data

Cities can apply to get access to aggregated trajectory-data collected with the fitness-app Strava. After a change of policy, Strava now offers this data for free to municipalities upon request. Uppsala is recommended to apply for this data and to use it to get acquainted and experiment with trajectory-based data. However, it has to be kept in mind that the sample is very biased and the results should not be used for planning decisions.

M: Use fitness-apps for small scale studies

To collect data on travel speeds or waiting time along a specific route, the number of trajectories needed is limited and representativeness of the sample is of little relevance. Trajectories can be collected by motivated cyclists using that route or even by city staff. For such small-scale measurement campaigns, fitness-apps that allow to export uploaded GPS-tracks are recommended.

N: Consider a dedicated tracking-app

If a heat-map of bicycle use or similar data is seen as valuable, dedicated tracking-apps such as *BikeCitizen* or *GéoVelo* should be considered. Plan and budget for marketing efforts to achieve a as high number of users as possible. Shorter, intense measuring campaigns with many participants, such as the Dutch *Fietstelweek* (bicycle counting week) are recommended. Compared with recruiting a smaller number of cyclists who track their journeys over a long time, a more concentrated effort with many participants is likely to produce more representative results.

O: Experiment with low-cost camera-based systems

Low-cost data-collection systems and crowdsourcing of measuring-sites as used in the Belgian *Telraam*-project have the potential to provide a large number of additional measuring points at little cost. It is therefore recommended to test and experiment with *Telraam*-sensors to gain experience with crowdsourced data acquisition.

9.5 INTERNATIONAL OUTLOOK AND COOPERATION

The cities of Copenhagen and Amsterdam are both advanced cycling cities with considerable experience in collecting and using data on bicycle- but also pedestrian-travel and could be used for inspiration and transfer of experience. Both make use of data from a variety of sensors and have internal support functions to process and analyse the collected data.

The key finding is that both cities see a value in collecting data systematically and over a long time. What data-acquisition methods are used is less relevant, both cities still primarily use conventional sensors and even manual counts are still used. Data from additional sources is used as a complement and integrated. Both cities have also established internal capacity and specialist know-how to process and analyse large datasets and to extract and present information in a way that makes is useful for others.

Apart from cities, also several international research institutions have been working with developing methods for collecting and integrating digital data about bicycle- and pedestrian-traffic and could be a source for further information, notably the University of Salzburg (Department of Geoinformatics, Mobility lab) which was a partner in this study. Uppsala University is currently (2022) cooperating with the University of Salzburg in a research project on digital mobility nudging⁶² (DyMoN – Dynamic Mobility Nudging) that has the potential to provide relevant results to the process of digitalisation of bicycle and pedestrian data.

Recommendations

O: Build up knowledge-exchange and cooperation with advanced cities.

Both Copenhagen and Amsterdam have been open to further contact and exchange with Uppsala. It is recommended to maintain that contact and to build up a long-term cooperation on the collection and use of pedestrian and cycling data.

P: Establish a contact with the DyMoN-project

Both the Universities of Uppsala and Salzburg are involved in the ongoing (2022) DyMoN-project that includes aspects of collection and processing of digital data on traffic. It is recommended to establish an exchange with the project to investigate possible synergies with the efforts of the Municipalities. Martin Loidl from the University of Salzburg is recommended as a first contact⁶³.

⁶² DyMoN – Dynamic Mobility Nudging. Research-project within the framework of JPI Urban Europa/ERA-NET. <https://dymon.eu/>

⁶³ Martin Loidl, Mobility Lab, University of Salzburg. Martin.Loidl@sbg.ac.at

10 Summary of recommendations

In this chapter, the developed recommendations are shortly summarised. The recommendations are marked with a level of priority and importance, based on our assessment of what would provide most value to Uppsala Municipality.

They are listed in a suggested order of implementation and partly build on each other. This does not imply that this sequence must be followed, nor that all recommended measures need to be implemented. Further, several measures can be implemented simultaneously, as parallel tracks.

The letter of the measure (in brackets) refers back to the more detailed description in chapter 9.

1: (A) Define what information is relevant and why.

Priority: High. Importance: High

Initiate an internal process to develop a better understanding of what information on pedestrian- and bicycle-traffic is needed, how the information could be used and what data is required.

2: (B) Define the (incremental) value of information

Priority: High. Importance: High

Discuss what value additional information on pedestrian- or bicycle-traffic can provide, as a basis to compare the costs and benefits of data acquisition.

2: (C) Generate a structured overview of existing data.

Priority: Intermediate. Importance: Intermediate

Investigate systematically what datasets on walking and cycling already exist within the municipality or are available.

3: (F) Create an internally accessible catalogue on available data

Priority: Intermediate. Importance: High

Create a digital, searchable catalogue over available data on bicycle- and pedestrian traffic and make it accessible within the municipality.

4: (D) Identify information gaps and gaps in availability

Priority: Intermediate. Importance: High

Compare the existing data (measure B) with the desired information (measure A) and identify any gaps.

5: (E) Choose suitable data and data-acquisitions methods

Priority: Intermediate. Importance: High

Once it has become clear what information is lacking or would provide additional value, identify possible data-sources and data-collecting methods. Compare different sources and methods and choose the most suitable.

6: (P) Establish a contact with the DyMoN-project

Priority: Intermediate. Importance: Low

Establish a contact with the ongoing DyMoN-project to explore possibilities for knowledge-exchange and cooperation. Martin Loidl from the University of Salzburg is recommended as a first contact.

7: (O) Build up knowledge-exchange and cooperation with advanced cities.

Priority: Intermediate. Importance: Intermediate

Establish an exchange of information on bicycle and pedestrian-measurement with other cities such as Copenhagen or Amsterdam.

8: (H) Create a common repository for storing bicycle- and pedestrian data

Priority: Intermediate. Importance: Very high

A common repository for bicycle- and pedestrian data should be created – either as a stand-alone database, as part of a larger repository for traffic-related data or as a part of a municipal data-lake. The exiting *Trafficweb* system could be used as a first step if data from permanent measuring stations can be integrated

9: (G) Create a common standard and routines for metadata

Priority: Low. Importance: Intermediate

Develop a standardised format and routines how to ensure that metadata always is properly associated to its corresponding dataset.

10: (J) Consider creating one or several inner-city rings of counters

Priority: Intermediate. Importance: Intermediate

Establish additional permanent counting station, strategically placed to form an “inner-city ring” to collect data on incoming- and outgoing cyclists.

11: (K) Choose camera-based systems when installing new counters

Priority: Intermediate Importance: Intermediate

Consider camera-based measuring systems when a new measuring point is established.

12: (L) Experiment with Strava-data

Priority: Low. Importance: Low

Apply for access to trajectory-data from the app-provider Strava or other open data-sources and experiment with the data to gain experience.

13: (I) Create a data-expert service

Priority: Low. Importance: Intermediate

Establish a position or task of a data expert to support city staff with the extraction, processing and presentation of bicycle- or pedestrian data.

14: (O) Experiment with low-cost camera-based systems

Priority: Low. Importance: Low

Test and experiment with *Telraam*-sensors to gain experience with crowdsourced data acquisition.

15: (M) Use fitness-apps for small scale studies

Priority: Low. Importance: Low

Use free fitness-apps with the possibility to export recorded trajectories for small-scale data collection and route-analysis.

16: (N) Consider a dedicated tracking-app

Priority: Low. Importance: Low

Consider dedicated tracking-apps such as *BikeCitizen* or *GéoVelo* if a heat-map of bicycle use or similar data is seen as valuable. Plan and budget for marketing efforts to achieve a as high number of users as possible.

Apendix 1: Summary of survey-responses

Introduction

To better understand the current situation in Uppsala, a short digital survey with city-staff involved in traffic planning has been conducted. Below, the questions and results are presented (in Swedish). Please observe that the sample was small (13) and that the participants were chosen based on their involvement in cycle- or pedestrian planning. The responses should only be interpreted as indicative.

Questions and responses

Vilken kategori tillhör din tjänst i kommunen?	Answer Choices	Responses
-Trafikplanering generellt		15,38% 2
-Trafikplanering fotgängare/cyklning (>50% av dina arbetsuppgifter)		0,00% 0
-Underhåll av gång-, cykel- och vägnätet		7,69% 1
-Miljöplanerare		0,00% 0
-Fysisk planering		0,00% 0
-Strategisk planering/analys		38,46% 5
-IT/ GIS		7,69% 1
-Kultur/idrott		7,69% 1
-Näringslivsutveckling		0,00% 0
Annat		23,08% 3
	Answered	13
	Skipped	0

På ett övergripande plan, hur viktigt bedömer du det är att Uppsala kommun samlar in och tillhandahåller data om fotgängar- och cykeltrafik?

Answer Choices	Responses	Count
Mycket viktigt	30,77%	4
Viktigt	38,46%	5
Mindre viktigt	0,00%	0
Mycket oviktigt	7,69%	1
Vet ej	23,08%	3
Varför?		11
	Answered	13
	Skipped	0

Vet du om det finns data om fotgängar- och cykeltrafik tillgänglig?

Answer Choices	Responses	Count
-Ja, inom min egen förvaltning	46,15%	6
-Ja, i andra förvaltningar	38,46%	5
-Nej	15,38%	2
	Answered	13
	Skipped	0

Vet du hur du kan få tillgång till datan		
Answer Choices	Responses	
Ja	76,92%	10
Nej	23,08%	3
	Answered	13
	Skipped	0

Använder du själv data om fotgängar- och cykeltrafik?		
Answer Choices	Responses	
Ja	38,46%	5
Nej	61,54%	8
	Answered	13
	Skipped	0

Vilka datakällor använder du dig av i din funktion?		Responses	
Answer Choices			
Inga		20,00%	1
Resvaneundersökningar		100,00%	5
Manuella trafikräkningar		0,00%	0
Tidsbegränsade trafikmätningar		40,00%	2
Permanent trafikmätningar		40,00%	2
Intervjustudier (t.ex. nöjdhetsstudier)		0,00%	0
Rapportering genom app eller webb (t.ex. skadeanmälan)		0,00%	0
GPS data från appar		20,00%	1
Annat		20,00%	1
	Answered		5
	Skipped		8

För vilket ändamål använder du denna data?		
Answer Choices	Responses	
Inget	0,00%	0
Infrastrukturplanering	20,00%	1
Evaluering av åtgärder	40,00%	2
Medborgardialog/medskapande	60,00%	3
Mätning och trafikplanering	40,00%	2
Kommunikation och marknadsföring	0,00%	0
Forskning	20,00%	1
Annat	20,00%	1
	Answered	5
	Skipped	8

Saknar du data om gång- och cykeltrafik som skulle underlätta ditt arbete?		
Answer Choices	Responses	
Ja	46,15%	
Nej	53,85%	
	Answered	
	Skipped	

Vilken typ av data som idag inte finns tillgänglig skulle vara mest till nytta i din funktion/dina arbetsuppgifter/uppdrag?

Answer Choices	Responses	
Ingen	16,67%	1
Resvaneundersökningar	50,00%	3
Manuella trafikräkningar	50,00%	3
Tidsbegränsade trafikmätningar	33,33%	2
Permanenta trafikmätningar	33,33%	2
Intervjustudier (t.ex. nöjdhetsstudier)	33,33%	2
Rapportering genom app eller webb (t.ex. skadeanmälan)	16,67%	1
GPS data från appar	50,00%	3
Annan data	33,33%	2
	Answered	6
	Skipped	7

I vilken typ av uppdrag/projekt skulle du använda denna data?

Answer Choices	Responses	
Ingen	16,67%	1
Infrastrukturplanering	16,67%	1
Evaluering av åtgärder	33,33%	2
Medborgardialog/medskapande	50,00%	3
Mätning och trafikplanering	50,00%	3
Kommunikation och marknadsföring	16,67%	1
Forskning	50,00%	3
Annat	33,33%	2
	Answered	6
	Skipped	7

Ser du problem med att samla in data om fotgängar- och cykeltrafik med tanke på data- och integritetsskydd?

Answer Choices	Responses	
Ja	41,67%	5
Nej	58,33%	7
Varför?		6
	Answered	12
	Skipped	1

Apendix 2: Summary of interview-responses

Introduction

To better understand the current situation in Uppsala, four interviews with selected stakeholders within the municipal organisation were conducted by phone. The interviews were semi-structured, with a set of pre-defined questions and the possibility to add comments freely. The interviewees represented the following positions:

- A: IT-strategist
- B: Operational transport planner
- C: Head of traffic unit
- D: Data analyst at central management unit
- E: Head of IT unit.

Below, the questions and answers are summarised (in Swedish)

Frågor och svar

Fråga 1: Vilken kategori tillhör din tjänst i kommunen?

A: It strateg 1,5 år jobbat med IoT

B: Trafikplanering, Stadsbyggnadsförvaltningen , avd gata, park , natur. Enheten trafik och samhälle

C: Enhetschef för Trafik och Samhälle i stadsbyggnadsförvaltningen; chef för de som planerar gång- och cykelinfrastruktur

D: Samhällsanalytiker, kommunledningskontoret. Huvuduppgifter. Befolkningsprognos, statistik på områdesnivå, valdistrikt.

E: Chief Information Officer, Uppsala municipality. Managing overall setup of IT and infrastructure, platforms, collecting data, business system etc. The IT-department has 118 employees, managing information systems, office systems, healthcare, education, schools.

Fråga 2: Om du jobbar med fotgängare eller cykling: På vilket sätt jobbar du med fotgängar- och cykeltrafik? Vad är dina arbetsuppgifter och hur länge har du jobbat med dessa frågor?

A: Jobbar med projekt: City as. A platform (Rise, 18 kommuner) nätverk med andra kommuner skr, dig, öppen data fokus, samlat kunskap för att förstå det. 1,5 år. Jag jobbar med att ta fram en målbild för helhetsbild inom iot

B: Jobbar med trafik, mobilitetsstrategi och godtstrafik. Ska jobba med gångtrafik på strategisk plan: handlingsplan för mobilitet och trafik.

3 saker som nämns där som jag ska jobba med:

- Anpassa rvu för mer kunskap om gång
 - Mäta gångföden i uppsala tätorten (inte definierad hur)
 - Kartlägga och definiera målpunkter och barriärer, ta fram ett huvudnät.
- Jobbat inte så länge (drygt ett år) med dessa frågor.

C: Chef för den enheten som jobbar med gång- och cykeltrafikinfrastruktur och hållbart resande. 10+ år erfarenhet av frågorna.

D: Konkret just nu jobbar jag inte med denna data (gc-data).

Trygghetsundersökning på områdesnivå genomför vi just nu. Även GIS data hanterar vi. Vi vill jobba närmare med kommunens översiktsplanering.

E: -

Fråga 3: På ett övergripande plan, hur viktigt bedömer du det är att Uppsala kommun samlar in och tillhandahåller data om fotgängar- och cykeltrafik? Skala 1-5

A: ?

B: Viktigt för oss själva och i vad vi har att arbeta med. Bra om vi vill att det ska finnas smarta appar eller lösningar från privata aktörer. Då måste man ha den datan och infrastrukturen för att kunna leverera.

C: Det är viktigt för att kunna motivera insatser som görs, följa upp och utvärdera. Idag finns tydlig politiskt stöd för att jobba med gång- och cykeltrafik, men det kan ändras och då är det särskilt viktigt att ha data som visar på betydelsen av dessa färdstätt. Skala 1-5 – 4 (Michaels tolkning)

D: Vi vill att verksamheter som båda jobbar med drift och byggnation ska göra datadriven beslut. Fördel om vi kan underbygga beslut med fakta. Inte bara enkät utan också data. Som inte bygger på urval.

Vi har byggt massa snabbcykelvägar men vet egentligen inte hur mycket de används. Bra med data. Det som kommunen gör/bygger ger kanske inte alltid de bästa förutsättningar för de flesta? Pga. ingen data. Riktade insatser kan man göra mycket bättre med data.

E: -

Fråga 4: Vet du om det finns data om fotgängar- och cykeltrafik tillgänglig?

A: Avd. på kommunledning. Sbk (Ola) samlar in en del data. Idag finns dock ingen struktur

B: Ja, inom min egen förvaltning och andra aktörer (citysamverkan).

De fasta cykelmätare exempelvis ger bra info/data. Används mycket.

Angående gångtrafik: Det som gjorts tidigare (före min tid) är att man har mätt (gångtrafik) på vissa punkter och kollat vad som händer (in- utföden gågata och stationen, vid en punkt under en viss tid). Citysamverkan har permanenta

mätare uppställt. Det är en mätare som räknar hur många besökare som finns under olika dagar. Det går exempelvis att jämföra speciella dagar under ett år. Vi kan ta del av deras data.

C: Ja, det finns några fasta mätpunkter för cykeltrafik med kontinuerlig mätning (3-4), vidare genomförs regelbundet slangmätningar. Särskilt de fasta mätpunkterna används för att följa cykeltrafikens utveckling.

Vidare finns RVU-data från 2000-2015, nu tas RVU-data fram i samverkan med Region Uppsala och inte av kommunen själv längre.

D: Inte mycket data tillgänglig egentligen. Vi genererar mycket data men har inte bra data-management. För vissa ställen har vi bra koll, för vissa sämre.

Vi gör slangmätningar. Observationsdata med räkning. Några fasta cykelmätare. Men ingen bra helhetsbild, ingen mätning på samma sätt övergripande. Har ingen kunskap om vad är säsongsvariationer. Ingen baseline matardata. Kan inte heller utvärdera insatser heller.

Uppsala citysamverkan har ett antal fasta mätpunkter i gågatan, 5-6 platser. Ingen aning hur data är uppbyggt. Skapar inget underlag för att kunna se större mönster – kvalitativt finns viss kunskap, men inte kvantifierad. Data visade t.ex. att färre personer rörde sig i gågatan under pandemin.

Vi har ingen generell bild över trafikflöden på gatusektions-nivån. Även om Uppsala centrum är ganska litet.

E: -

Fråga 5: Jag vet hur jag kan få tillgång till datan

A: Finns ingen infrastruktur för dataöverföring just nu. Krävs mer utredning.

B: Ja.

C: Ja

D: Ja. Men det finns inget enkelt sätt att dela data idag.

E:

Fråga 6: Använder du själv data om fotgängar- och cykeltrafik? För vad använder du denna data?

A: Inte idag.

B: Ja. RVU-data framförallt, och olycksstatistik från STRADA. Senaste RVU 2020 är köpt från regionen som gjorde en RVU för hela regionen. Det kanske har gjorts något annat tidigare. Mätdata från Citysamverkan. Använder det till alla kategorier ovan. Det handlar mycket om att ta reda på vad vi ska göra: bygga nytt, bättre, informera, var rör sig folk? Vilka som rör sig? Barn och äldre rör sig mindre och mindre (RVU resultat), intressant att veta varför? Handlar om att fler ska gå. Allt från infra till kommunikation

C: Ja, eller snarare enheten jag ansvarar för. Datan används för att följa cykeltrafikens generella utveckling, göra prioriteringar, när det finns behov av beläggningsarbete, saknande länkar (MK – oklart hur den befintliga datan kan visa det; mer önskemål än faktisk användning?)

För: Infratrstrukturplanering – ja. Evaluering av åtgärder: delvis, begränsad. Medborgardialog: nej. Monitoring och trafikplanering – ja, följa cykeltrafikens utveckling. Kommunikation, marknadsföring – ja, mätdata redovisas i Uppsalas cykelbokslut

D: Använde för trygghetsundersökningar. Cykel- och gångdata är bara stödande för att se hur många människor som är där.

Jag har ingen egen verksamhetsdata. De som har det ska också kunna hantera det. Ex. utbildningsförvaltningen har koll på skolfrånvaro. För oss är det intressant att aggregera på områdesnivå och inte skolnivå. Med cykeldata skulle man kunna se varifrån de kommer...kan man påverka det med insatser?

E: Nej

Fråga 7: Saknar du data om gång- och cykeltrafik som skulle underlätta ditt arbete?

A: –

B: Ja: gångflöden, intervjustudier

C: Delvis data om användarna – t.ex. hur många barn går eller cyklar till skolan, varför, varför inte.

Kvalitativ information – Hur många cyklar för att de inte har något annat val (ingen bil, dålig kollektivtrafik mm), för att det är snabbt etc. Vad är motiven att gå/cykla eller inte göra det. Var ligger hindren?

En del enkäter har gjorts (Cyklistvelometer mm), men kanske inte direkt kopplat till specifik infrastruktur.

D: Vi har dålig koll på flöden...att få det totala genomströmningen (av gång/cykel) vore bra. Även förändringen över dygnet.

Bra masterdata som man kan använda för mycket. Jag kommer aldrig följa upp den datan men kan behöva den datan utifrån andra samband.

E: Nej

Fråga 8: Ser du problem med att samla in data om fotgängar- och cykeltrafik med tanke på data- och integritetsskydd?

A: Integriteten är viktig. Hur säkerställer vi integriteten?

B: Nej, varför?: vi ska inte använda det för något annat än planering. Kan vara ett dilemma men det finns sätt att lösa det.

C: GDPR behöver följas, men förutom det egentligen inte.

D: Nej, tror inte det. Finns inga system där det blir problem (inte på individnivå). man ska inte vara fast vid ett system. Ska ha kompetens. Inom vården är integritetsfrågan mycket värre. Men det här är ganska allmängiltiga data. Det kommer antagligen alltid finnas bortfall

E: -

Fråga 9: Vilka personer, företag eller institutioner skulle kunna ha nytta av data om fotgängar- och cykeltrafik?

A: -

B: Främst offentliga aktörer. Men även Citysamverkan, app utvecklare, kollektivtrafikaktörer, företag generellt.

C: Om det fanns aktuella flödesdata på avsnittsnivå skulle det kunna vara intressant för t.ex. affärsutvecklare eller butiker.

D: Data om hur personer rör sig med cykel och till fots: bra för butiker, kommunal verksamhet, parkskötsel? Vi är inte där än att andra kan bygga massa appar. Universitet mer intressant.

E:

Fråga 10: Hur ser du på Open data?

A: Att göra datan tillgänglig är svårt. Borde jobbar mer med öppen data. Vi har lite Kolada data och baskartan på hemsidan men det arbetet har stått stilla sen 2015.

B: Bra, förutsatt att det är anonymt och att vi har ett syfte med det. Har varit diskussion om man ska dela data om biltillverkare

C:

D: Öppen data: inte fullt ut i nuläget.

E: Anonymizing is important, then no problem.

Öppna kommentarer

A: Problem med data infrastruktur just nu: Det behövs en ägare för datan. Bristen av behov. vilken data ska vi ha? det kan inte bara vara temp och vatten.

B: Tidigare så jobbade jag med trafiksignaler och räknare som kan samla in data. Där kan man samla in ett helt års statistik utan att det är problem...så detta görs redan.

Ibland så raderar man bara utan att veta vad som har hänt. Problemet är att det ofta inte finns en person / enhet som tar hand om datan. Inte tydligt.

När man köper en tjänst måste beslutet också grundas på en bas. Måste ha person som vet hur man ska göra. Det är inget problem, och handlar bara om att vi måste veta vad vi ska ha det för. Sen kan vi ha mycket användning av datan.

C:

- Uppföljning har utvecklingspotential.
- Generell läggs för lite tid på analyser.
- Bra gång- cykeldata kan vara relevant i planering, t.ex. om en cykelbana kan smalnas av eller tas bort, då är det bra med data för att kunna argumentera emot.
- Driftenheten borde ha nytta av datan för att kunna motivera prioriteringar.
- Resultat från flödesmätningar för bil läggs in i NVDB (TRV flödeskarta)
- Det pågår ett samarbete med VTI kring cykelmätning, Tommy Eriksson vet mer.

D: Någonstans måste vi hamna vid ett brytpunkt att det är billigare att hantera datainhämtning och hantering övergripande och inte som punktinsatser .

Det är en väldigt fin vision med digitaliseringen, men idag finns ingen plattform för data eller något enkelt sätt att dela data. I vår GIS plattform finns vissa möjligheter att ta emot annan data.

Vi har ingen underbyggd infrastruktur för att kunna hantera data. Trafikenheten skulle ha nytta av det redan nu. Även för ruttoptimering, t.ex. om man gräver upp någonstans, för flödesomledning.

Också för att veta vilka gator som används mycket, för att kunna styra insatser.

Viktigt i arbetet framåt: Ibland är simpel better. Man skulle i tidigt skede kunna visualisera i GIS ett antal cases för folk som inte riktigt förstår vad datan innebär.

Det finns ett gap mellan IT-infrastruktur och faktiska planerare. De behöver föras tillsammans för att bättre och systematiskt kunna arbeta med data.

E: We have a unit to setup a IoT platform for the city, information management around IoT. Challenges - How can we build the digitized city, digitalization to collect data, process, real time view?

Information management is critical. If there is a good structure for information management, new sensors/data sources can be added in an efficient way, also commercial products

We are using the GIS systems quite extensively with 3D view and digital twin. We're in the forefront in Uppsala, engineers develop inside the municipality. Tight connection to ESRI. Even trash bins are integrated with the platform, with mobile devices inside trash cans.

Appendix 3: Questions and answers from workshop 1

Introduction

Workshop 1 was conducted digitally on the 25th of August 2021. From Uppsala municipality, 16 persons from different departments participated.

During the workshop, the participants were asked to answer a series of questions on their wishes concerning data about bicycle and pedestrian traffic. The questions and answers are presented below (in Swedish).

Fråga 1: Vilken information om gång och cykling i Uppsala skulle du vilja ha?

SVAR:

- *Hur nyttjar man gc-nätet? Dvs bekräfta det vi tror för att kunna planera bättre.*
- *Restider och trängsel. Hur ser de kortaste resvägarna ut? Det gör att vi kan styra.*
- *Tillgängligöra bästa resrutt för cyklister. Koppla ihop flera datakällor t ex luftkvalitet för bl a info till gång- och cyklister. Säsongsvariationer och utveckling över tid.*
- *Hur ser rörelsemönster ut och var uppehåller man sig och hur kan det kopplas till trygghet.*
- *Slitage- och underhållsbehov vid våra friluftsområden.*
- *Realtidsdata på sikt. Att man kan koppla ihop olika data med varandra.*
- *Att kunna jämföra data från olika platser. Sätta de i relation.*
- *Jämförelse mellan färdmedel önskvärt*
- *Argumentation för satsningar i bl.a. d-planer. Kan ta bättre beslut och dra bättre slutsatser av insatser i gaturum (space-syntax)*
- *Finns ingen information om flöden*
- *Data för att få en helhetsbild om trafikflöden i stan*
- *Uppföljning*
- *Nollmätning: när man bygger ett nytt kvarter/område*
- *Mätning över tid. Vilken variation under vissa säsonger?*
- *Sätta annan data i relation till flödesdata (befolkningstäthet t.ex.).*
- *Hur vistas folk i gaturum? Säkerhetsaspekt*
- *Nulägeskunskap i relation till mål som sammanhängande stad etc., men vi har lite kunskap om rörelsen i staden. Vi vet inte var de faktiska barriärerna ligger avseende handling. Är det vissa platser som undviks? Av vissa grupper? Vilka målgrupper rör sig var? Vilka grupper rör sig var?*
- *Mål Goda Vardagslivet - hur skapar vi enklare vardagsliv, 15-min staden. Hur fungerar rörelsen i relation till det målet, t.ex. målet att det ska finnas en lekplats inom 5 min - men används den faktiskt?. Identifiera rörelsen - kopplat till grupper, men även bara rörelsen.*
- *Planeringsideal finns, men vet vi vad vi gör? Vad är underlaget för vald stadsstruktur.*
- *Hur folk rör sig, vilka platser besöks.*

- *Hur ser utvecklingen av gång- och cykling ut? Tillförlitlig data kring utvecklingen av gång- och cykel.*
- *Var cyklar folk, vilka stråk, var finns höga flöden? För att kunna göra bedömningar var det behövs åtgärder. Kunna anpassa infrastrukturen till efterfrågan.*
- *Före- och eftermätningar vid en specifik åtgärd - effektuppföljning;*
- *Se till att målen har en förankring i verkligheten, att de är möjliga att uppnå. Även för att förstå vilka åtgärder som kan vara meningsfulla.*
- *Jobba med brottsförebyggande planering - hur många rör sig. För att försöka förstå siffrorna bättre.*
- *Gående - finns ingen tydlig uppdelning mellan gå och vistas. Hur mycket rör sig folk i olika stråk, finns det förutsättningar. För att planera var det ska byggas bänkar etc. - i praktiken.*

Fråga 2: Hur kan den samlade informationen göras tillgängligt?

- *SBF har behovet och behöver veta vilka data. Även ansvaret att kvalitetsgranska och att den är verifierbar.*
- *KLK och IT om var samlas datat och ett business intelligence system. IT vet hur det bör paketeras för att kunna nyttjas. Vi vill skapa öppen data som kan användas av andra.*
- *Case-by-case om vem som ansvarar för inhämtning, bearbetning. Lagringen och spridningen ligger hos IT.*
- *Bred fråga. Det beror på hur vi får datat. Molnbaserat eller egna servrar. Vi kan skapa en datalake. En central IT-funktion*
- *Aggregera data. Data management. Det måste finnas med i budget och driftsättning. Förståelse at det är viktigt. En del av verksamheten.*
- *Visa att det kan generera förbättringar*
- *Finns ingen kunskap om datagenerering i verksamheter. Ofta konsulter som kommer in*
- *Det saknas en gemensam plattform för att få tillgång till data generellt.*
- *Sätta flödesdata i relation med drift. Effektivisera driften.*
- *Öppendata: tillgång väldigt personberoende i kommunen. Finns inga systematiserade sätt. Arbete pågår för att förbättra tillgången*
- *Vi behöver förstå behovet. Det är ingen som använder den typen av trafikdata. Case skulle göra tydligt för vilka ändamål datan kan användas.*
- *Det saknas kvalitetssäkring av data*
- *Det finns brister i samverkan och kommunikation. Det behövs en ägare för datan.*
- *Det skulle behöva någon form av datarevision. Kartläggning. Datakatalog. Arbete som pågår.*
- *Svår fråga - även bekymmer inom andra enheter att sprida data och göra det tillgängligt. Vissa vill ha det enkel och samlat, andra vill kunna göra analyser själv.*
- *All grunddatan ska vara samlat i ETT system som går att komma åt, men även en plattform med mer aggregerad data, snabbt tillgängligt;*
- *Bredare användning kräver bearbetning och förenkling.*
- *Ev någon form av it-plattform för samlad statistik där alla kan komma åt, både inifrån och utifrån*
- *Allt som är individkopplad behöver vara sekretess-skydd.*

- *Det behövs mer enade system för information - måste kopplas till karta, ska gå att få fram lätt.*
- *Överlagring av olika typer av information behöver kunna göras.*
- *Koppla till karta.*
- *Inzoomningsbar.*
- *Om det ska vara bred tillgängligt - fokusera på några nyckeltal, presentera dessa.*
- *Det behöver vara så enkelt det går;*
- *Kartbaserad system med bearbetad data som är lättillgängligt; ev med dashboards.*
- *Dashboard med nyckeltal.*
- *Vem ska hålla i det ? Trafik & samhälle... IT kan behöva vara med för att få ut det på nätet eller för att få in information.*

Fråga 3: Vem ska få tillgång, vems data används?

- *Öppna data.*
- *Vi bör kanske dock kvalitetssäkra data innan den blir öppen.*
- *Ja, vi kan använda andra data, myndigheter men även andra privata. Vi måste ha koll på kvaliteten dock.*
- *Öppna API'er.*
- *Finns oändligt många man kan tänka sig.*
- *Data som inte är säkra på täckning och kvalitet. Det måste vara tydligt .*
- *Kunskap om datan viktigt. Den som äger datan ska ha koll*
- *Juridiskt: Får vi dela data? Vilken data äger vi?*
- *Principiellt ska all data vara öppen. Den behöver aggregeras*
Data från andra: kommer ofta från konsulter. Ja, om vi kan säkra kvalitén.
Det kanske kan hända att någon extern kan använda datan på ett bättre sätt (ifrågasätta politiska beslut).
- *I principen tillgängligöra så mycket data som möjligt, i aggregerad; kan spara arbete*
- *Inget problem på aggregerad nivå; det är farligt att vilja hålla på saker*
- *Aktörer som kan vara intressanta - universitet, forskning, intresseorganisationer, näringsliv - kopplat till lokalisering; kan finnas goda möjligheter att tillhandahålla unikt data för näringsliv*
- *Andra aktörer - universitetet, har gjort mobiltelefon-studier, mobiloperatörer*

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